

Evolution of Methods for the Oxidation of Primary Alcohols to Carboxylic Acids: From Metal Oxides to Biocatalysis

Jonas Spang,[‡] Francesco Mascia,[‡] and Wolfgang Kroutil*[‡]

Cite This: *JACS Au* 2026, 6, 659–677

Read Online

ACCESS |

Metrics & More

Article Recommendations

ABSTRACT: Carboxylic acids are central building blocks in fine chemical synthesis. Although the direct oxidation of primary alcohols to carboxylic acids appears straightforward from a retrosynthetic perspective, it is often associated with significant challenges. In this Perspective, we discuss concepts of one-pot approaches for the oxidation of primary alcohols to carboxylic acids. These approaches are grouped into chemical and biocatalytic concepts, which are structured according to the stoichiometric oxidant employed. The evolution of these methods is traced from traditional chemical oxidations to modern catalytic and biocatalytic strategies, underscoring the parallel shift in oxidant selection and the resulting improvements in selectivity, practical utility, and sustainability.

KEYWORDS: Oxidation, Primary Alcohols, Carboxylic Acids, Metal Oxides, Chemocatalysis, Biocatalysis

INTRODUCTION

Carboxylic acids are ubiquitous structural motifs in chemical synthesis and represent an essential functional group in bulk and fine chemicals. For instance, over 450 pharmaceuticals contain carboxylic acid moieties, including antibiotics, anticoagulants, lipid-lowering agents, and nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs).¹ A survey of GMP-scale reactions revealed that carboxylic acids were obtained preferentially by interconversion of carboxylic acid derivatives (e.g., esters, nitriles), which represented the single most common class of reactions (~26%). In contrast, direct oxidation of primary alcohols was underrepresented,² thus, the seemingly intuitive strategy of oxidizing primary alcohols to carboxylic acids is often considered a synthetic challenge, especially on an industrial scale. Therefore, instead of relying on primary alcohol oxidation, carboxylic acids are generally obtained by hydrolyzing esters or nitriles, since these routes are often considered safer, cleaner, and more robust compared to oxidation reactions. The reluctance to oxidize primary alcohols likely stems from the fact that many conventional protocols rely on nonchemoselective reagents and harsh conditions. These reagents and conditions often generate side products and significant amounts of waste.³ To address these issues, catalytic methods have emerged in organic synthesis to improve selectivity, efficiency, and sustainability.⁴ In parallel, rapid developments in biocatalysis have enabled complementary routes allowing oxidations under mild and potentially environmentally benign conditions.^{5–14} Here we provide a

systematic overview and evaluation of chemical and biocatalytic concepts for the oxidation of primary alcohols to carboxylic acids. In both cases, the methods are grouped according to the stoichiometric oxidant employed, and for the biocatalytic section, the type of enzyme used is also considered.

CHEMICAL OXIDATION METHODS

In general, the oxidation of primary alcohols to carboxylic acids proceeds via a two-step process involving an aldehyde intermediate (Figure 1). From a thermodynamic point of view, the oxidation of a primary alcohol is exergonic ($\Delta G < 0$) across a wide pH range. The driving force increases significantly at higher pH values, as the reaction is a proton-coupled electron transfer, and depending on the pH, the formation of a resonance-stabilized carboxylate further may drive the reaction.^{4,15} However, heating is often required to overcome the kinetic barrier associated with the initial oxidation step. Almost all methods rely on the presence of water, which is needed for the equilibrium between the aldehyde and the corresponding hydrate, as the latter intermediate is actually oxidized to the acid. Among selected

Received: October 30, 2025

Revised: January 15, 2026

Accepted: January 20, 2026

Published: February 2, 2026

Figure 1. Chemical methods for the oxidation of primary alcohols to the corresponding carboxylic acids.

classical chemical oxidation methods, we include examples ranging from noncatalytic processes with metalate oxidants to catalytic approaches using organic or inorganic oxidants (ideally, benign ones such as hydrogen peroxide or molecular oxygen), electrochemical systems, and dehydrogenation strategies.

Metalates

Noncatalytic oxidation methods employing stoichiometric amounts of (oxo)metalates, such as Cr and Mn oxides, have been applied not only on a laboratory scale but also for some industrial applications. This is not surprising, as first-row

transition metals in their higher oxidation states act as powerful oxidizing agents, as also detailed in a recent review.⁴

The Jones oxidation¹⁶ is the most prominent example of chromium-based oxidation (Figure 2a). In practice, the “Jones reagent”, prepared from chromium(VI) trioxide in concentrated sulfuric acid, is typically used as an aqueous acetone solution. Under many discussed mechanisms, the chromium(VI) trioxide (“Jones reagent”) reacts with the primary alcohol substrate, forming a Cr(VI)-alkoxide ester intermediate,¹⁷ which undergoes E2-type β -elimination, cleaving the C–H bond in the rate-determining step.¹⁸ Jones oxidation typically proceeds with reasonable selectivity, since both steps, the oxidation of the primary alcohol and of the aldehyde hydrate intermediate, proceed via the ester-mediated C–H cleavage. For instance, propargylic¹⁹ or higher functionalized chiral alcohols²⁰ can be oxidized to carboxylic acids, achieving medium to high yields.

The classical Corey–Schmidt oxidation typically converts primary alcohols to aldehydes; however, adjustment of reaction conditions allows access to the corresponding carboxylic acids (Figure 2b). Corey–Schmidt-type oxidations using chromium(VI) trioxide conducted in anhydrous or wet pyridine/DMF at ambient temperature,³ generate pyridinium dichromate (PDC), which efficiently oxidizes nonallylic or nonbenzylic primary alcohols to carboxylic acids.²¹ However, both the Jones and Corey–Schmidt-type oxidations typically rely on toxic chromium(VI)–oxo species, leading to stoichiometric quantities of chromium waste and often suffering from the occurrence of unspecific side reactions, as well as dimeric esters.³ Nevertheless, the Jones oxidation remains a robust and often high-yielding method that is frequently used in total synthesis.²²

Figure 2. Oxidation of primary alcohols to the corresponding acids using selected (oxo)metalates. (a) Jones oxidation employing the Jones reagent¹⁶ for the selective oxidation of propargylic¹⁹ or chiral alcohols.²⁰ (b) Pyridinium dichromate (PDC) oxidation, commonly referred to as the Corey–Schmidt-type oxidation.²¹ (c) KMnO₄ oxidation of primary alcohols under basic²³ or acidic²⁵ conditions.

(2) catalytic methods using organic or inorganic oxidants

Figure 3. Catalytic oxidation of primary alcohols to carboxylic acids by selected organic or inorganic oxidants. (a) Jones-type oxidation of primary alcohols catalyzed by CrO_3 using H_5IO_6 as a terminal oxidant.²⁹ (b) Tetra-*n*-propylammonium perruthenate (TPAP)-catalyzed oxidation using *N*-methylmorpholin-*N*-oxide (NMO) as the stoichiometric oxidant.³¹ (c) Oxidation by nitric acid using sodium nitrite as the catalyst.^{32,33} (d) Cu(I)-catalyzed oxidation using *tert*-butyl hydroperoxide ($t\text{BuOOH}$).³⁴ (e) 4-Methoxy-TEMPO-catalyzed Anelli oxidation using potassium hypochlorite.³⁵ (f) TEMPO-catalyzed oxidation of primary alcohols in a two-step reaction, one-pot process.³⁶

In addition to chromium chemistry, permanganate(VII)-based methods are often used for the conversion of primary alcohols to carboxylic acids (Figure 2c). Permanganate oxidations under basic conditions²³ proceed through hydrogen atom abstraction or single-electron transfer, generating Mn–O intermediates and carbon-centered radicals.²⁴ This pathway often leads to side reactions and overoxidation of other C–H bonds, making permanganate a rather unselective oxidant. The oxidations carried out in water under basic²³ as well as sometimes acidic²⁵ conditions, lead to moderate yields. Thus, poor chemoselectivity and unfavorable atom economy arising from stoichiometric MnO_2 byproducts hinder the broader applicability of potassium permanganate-mediated oxidations.²⁶

Stoichiometric oxidations using metalates are considered unattractive due to poor atom economy, high E-factors (defined as the amount of waste generated per kilogram of product), and the generation of significant amounts of hazardous waste.²⁷ As a result, only a few industrial processes still rely on stoichiometric chromate oxidants, while most modern large-scale oxidations have shifted toward catalytic methods.²⁸

Organic and Inorganic Oxidants

Besides noncatalytic stoichiometric oxidations with (oxo)-metalates, several catalytic approaches have been developed to improve selectivity, efficiency, and sustainability in the oxidation of primary alcohols to carboxylic acids. The Jones-type oxidation employing catalytic amounts of CrO_3 with

Figure 4. Selected examples for the oxidation of primary alcohols using H₂O₂ as the stoichiometric oxidant. (a) Na₂WO₄-catalyzed oxidation using H₂O₂.⁴¹ (b) Co(II)-catalyzed oxidation using H₂O₂.⁴² (c) Pt(0) nanoparticles supported on silica catalyze the oxidation of a wide range of aliphatic, benzylic, and allylic primary alcohols to the corresponding carboxylic acids in continuous flow.⁴³ (d) Polymeric peroxybenzoic acid-catalyzed primary alcohol oxidation to acids.⁴⁴

periodic acid (H₅IO₆) as the terminal oxidant affords high yields of carboxylic acids (Figure 3a).²⁹ However, as mentioned before, the broader utility of chromium-catalyzed Jones-type oxidation is limited by the generation of toxic chromium waste. Tetra-*n*-propylammonium perruthenate (TPAP) with *N*-methylmorpholine *N*-oxide (NMO) typically oxidizes primary alcohols to aldehydes under mild conditions.³⁰ Reaction tuning to improve acid formation can be achieved by employing higher catalyst loading, an excess of NMO, and promoting geminal diol formation (Figure 3b).³¹

Oxidation via nitric acid catalyzed by NaNO₂ is scalable and effective for forming carboxylic acids (Figure 3c).^{32,33} However, the medium is corrosive, and the reaction selectivity is moderate, which can result in overoxidation.

Copper-catalyzed systems with *tert*-butyl hydroperoxide (*t*BuOOH) generally oxidize primary alcohols to aldehydes, but acid formation is occasionally observed under forcing conditions (e.g., 5 equiv of *t*BuOOH) (Figure 3d).³⁴ The high stoichiometric amount of oxidant and waste is a drawback of this protocol.

In contrast to the methods discussed above, nitroxyl radical-mediated oxidations constitute highly efficient methodologies with proven applicability from laboratory to industrial scale. Anelli and co-workers showed that 4-methoxy-2,2,6,6-tetramethylpiperidin-1-oxyl (4-methoxy-TEMPO) in combination with aqueous NaOCl under biphasic, buffered conditions (pH 8.6) enables the selective oxidation of primary alcohols to

aldehydes. TEMPO undergoes reversible oxidation to the oxoammonium cation, which is generally proposed to act as the active oxidant, abstracting a hydride (or proton-coupled electron) from the alcohol to form the aldehyde, while regenerating TEMPO via reoxidation. Notably, under otherwise identical conditions, aldehydes undergo subsequent oxidation to carboxylic acids in the presence of bromide ions and a quaternary ammonium phase-transfer catalyst (Figure 3e).³⁵

A broad range of TEMPO-based methods has been developed and partially applied in industry over the past decades. For instance, a two-step, one-pot oxidation method using NaOCl and NaClO₂ as stoichiometric oxidants was developed at Fujisawa Pharmaceutical Co., Ltd. (Figure 3f).³⁶ Optimization of pH and sequential addition of the oxidant enabled multikilogram synthesis of carboxylic acids in high yields. Although partially used at a larger scale, TEMPO-mediated oxidation using NaOCl and NaClO₂ faces challenges such as the cost of TEMPO,³⁷ difficulties in catalyst recycling,³⁸ and the more demanding downstream processing associated with halide-containing waste.³⁹

Hydrogen Peroxide as the Oxidant

Using hydrogen peroxide as the oxidant offers a high potential for the development of sustainable oxidation methods, as only water as a benign coproduct is generated when using suitable catalysts.⁴⁰ Phase-transfer-catalysis systems have been intro-

(4) catalytic methods using molecular oxygen

a TEMPO-catalyzed oxidation by O₂oxidant: O₂

catalyst: TEMPO with Cu or Fe additives

oxidant: O₂

catalyst: Cu(Laccase) / TEMPO

oxidant: O₂

catalyst: Pd-Bi-Te/C

oxidant: O₂

catalyst: TPPT

R = 4-*t*Bu, 4-CF₃, 4-OMe, 4-OH, 4-Cl, 4-Br, 3-I, 4-F

Figure 5. Selected examples for the oxidation of primary alcohol to the corresponding carboxylic acids employing molecular oxygen as oxidant. (a) TEMPO together with Fe- or Cu-catalyzed oxidation.^{53,54} (b) Chemoenzymatic oxidation using the TEMPO/laccase system.⁵⁶ (c) Heterogeneous Pd-Bi-Te/C-catalyzed oxidation.⁵⁷ (d) Photocatalytic oxidation using 2,4,6-triphenylpyrylium tetrafluoroborate (TPPT) catalyst.⁵⁸

duced for this purpose, with a notable example relying on Na₂WO₄ (Figure 4a).⁴¹ Ammonium hydrogensulfate is essential for high reactivity, with the acidity of the counteranion playing a decisive role in stabilizing the peroxotungstate species and facilitating their transfer into the organic phase. Maximum activity was achieved at an initial pH of ~2 and elevated temperatures (~90 °C). These conditions stabilize the peroxotungstate species and accelerate the conversion of aldehydes via their hydrates to the corresponding carboxylic acids, resulting in high yields.

Co(II)-salen and related complexes efficiently catalyze the oxidation of benzylic and aliphatic primary alcohols to carboxylic acids using 30% hydrogen peroxide in acetonitrile at elevated temperatures (~80 °C), affording good yields (Figure 4b).⁴² Furthermore, immobilized cobalt-based catalysts have been developed, with a notable example being cobalt(II) thioporphyrine immobilized on magnetic silica, facilitating the selective oxidation of benzylic alcohols to benzoic acids in an aqueous medium using hydrogen peroxide as the oxidant.⁴⁵

Polyoxometalates have attracted attention as recyclable peroxo catalysts. It was demonstrated that Zn-substituted polyoxometalates promote clean alcohol-to-acid oxidations with hydrogen peroxide under microwave irradiation, highlighting the role of heteropolyacid acidity in stabilizing reactive peroxo intermediates.⁴⁶ More recently, amino acid-modified Keggin-type polyoxometalates were shown to selectively

oxidize primary aliphatic alcohols such as 1-propanol to propionic acid in aqueous media,⁴⁷ while tungstate-based polyoxometalates immobilized on porous aromatic frameworks delivered high yields of benzoic acids under heterogeneous aqueous conditions.⁴⁸

In parallel, noble metal nanoparticles have emerged as effective heterogeneous catalysts for hydrogen peroxide-driven oxidations. Pt(0) nanoparticles supported on silica were reported for the oxidation of a wide range of aliphatic, benzylic, and allylic primary alcohols to the corresponding carboxylic acids in continuous flow, with isolated yields reaching up to 98% (Figure 4c).⁴³ In addition to transition metal catalysis, metal-free hydrogen peroxide activation strategies were developed. For instance, peroxybenzoic acid was formed in situ upon treatment of polymeric benzoic acid with hydrogen peroxide. The reactive polymeric peracid was capable of oxidizing primary alcohols to acids with high yields and selectivity (Figure 4d).⁴⁴

Yet, oxidation of primary alcohols using hydrogen peroxide has been mainly carried out at the laboratory scale.⁴⁹ Indeed, these routes remain a niche but can be attractive when the advantages of aqueous media, low halide and metal content, and higher safety in flow systems outweigh the issues related to handling hydrogen peroxide and potentially dangerous peroxo species.⁵⁰ Broader application will depend on the development of robust, recyclable heterogeneous catalysts, corrosion-

Figure 6. Oxidation of primary alcohols to the corresponding carboxylic acid by electrochemical methods. (a) Anodic Ni(OH)₂-mediated oxidation in alkaline solution.⁶⁹ (b) Oxidation of heteroaromatic primary alcohols with a NiOOH-coated anode.⁷⁰ (c) 4-Acetamido-TEMPO (ACT)-mediated electrochemical dehydrogenation of primary alcohols.⁷¹

resistant operation conditions at pH 1–3, metered hydrogen peroxide delivery, or in situ hydrogen peroxide generation.

Molecular Oxygen as the Oxidant

Similar to hydrogen peroxide, molecular oxygen is an oxidant of choice for potential sustainable oxidations due to its abundance, atom economy, and benign reaction coproduct (water).⁵¹ Historically, large-scale hydrocarbon oxidations with O₂ enabled industrial carboxylic acid production. For instance, in 1920, early paraffin oxidation studies showed that diluted O₂ or air streams resulted in higher fatty acid yields, although overoxidation and byproduct formation also occurred.⁵²

Many catalytic methods have been developed for the activation of molecular oxygen. For instance, an Fe/TEMPO system [Fe(NO₃)₃·9H₂O/TEMPO/KCl] achieved aerobic oxidation of alcohols to carboxylic acids at room temperature (Figure 5a, left part).⁵³ The Fe(NO₃)₃/TEMPO catalytic system generates an oxoammonium species that oxidizes alcohols to aldehydes via β-H elimination. Subsequently, Fe-mediated hydration and further oxidation convert the aldehyde into carboxylic acid, with O₂ serving as the terminal oxidant and NO_x cycling the Fe²⁺/Fe³⁺ redox couple. Notably, the Fe³⁺-mediated hydration of the aldehyde forms a metalated hydrate, which subsequently undergoes β-H elimination, yielding the carboxylic acid. A broad scope of primary alcohols bearing various groups like esters, ethers, halides, heterocycles, and alkynes was oxidized to the corresponding carboxylic acids, including the gram-scale synthesis of phloemic acid.

In a complementary method, primary alcohols were efficiently oxidized to acids employing Cu(NO₃)₂·3H₂O (10 mol %) with catalytic TEMPO and KHSO₄ under O₂ (Figure 5a, right part).⁵⁴ The sulfate was shown to be essential for aldehyde hydration, consequently accelerating the overall aldehyde-to-acid step. Primary alcohols containing aliphatic, benzylic, alkynyl, amino, as well as sterically demanding groups were oxidized in high isolated yields. However, both the iron- or copper-dependent TEMPO catalytic systems require rather high catalyst loading and rely on high amounts of additives, which may reduce the overall process efficiency.

Chemoenzymatic TEMPO-based protocols were developed, with the multicopper oxidase laccase continuously regenerating the oxoammonium species, which catalyzed the primary alcohol oxidation. Whereas conventional laccase–mediator systems typically stall at the aldehyde stage,⁵⁵ solvent engineering using citrate buffer promoted aldehyde hydration and enabled efficient conversion of 5-hydroxymethylfurfural to 2,5-furandicarboxylic acid with up to 94% yield at 200 mM substrate loading (Figure 5b).⁵⁶ The method operates under mild aqueous conditions and is scalable, though activity remains strongly buffer-dependent, and the substrate scope was only shown for aromatic alcohols.

A Pd–Bi–Te/C heterogeneous catalyst was applied to mediate aerobic oxidation of benzylic, aliphatic, and heteroaryl primary alcohols to the corresponding carboxylic acids, operating under O₂ at 50 °C in continuous flow (Figure 5c).⁵⁷ Bi and Te promoters act synergistically to suppress aldehyde accumulation and inhibit Pd deactivation. Primary alcohols were oxidized to carboxylic acids with yields of >90% across a broad substrate range in continuous-flow packed-bed reactors.

A direct, metal-free alternative was introduced by employing a photoredox strategy with 2,4,6-triphenylpyrylium tetrafluoroborate (TPPT). Under blue LED irradiation, excited TPPT activates O₂ through two orthogonal pathways. Initially, a single-electron transfer generates superoxide for the alcohol-to-aldehyde oxidation step, while energy transfer produces singlet oxygen that converts aldehydes to carboxylic acids. This dual activation enabled sequential oxidation, affording benzoic acids in up to 96% yield (Figure 5d).⁵⁸ However, reduced oxidation efficiency for certain substituted benzyl alcohols was observed,⁵⁸ and like many photoredox protocols, challenges in scale-up due to light penetration issues may need to be addressed. Several additional aerobic primary alcohol oxidation strategies were reported.

For instance, Au/mesoporous TiO₂ in water converts primary alcohols to the corresponding acids using O₂ as the sole oxidant.⁵⁹ Furthermore, organocatalytic oxidation meth-

Figure 7. Formal oxidation of primary alcohols by catalytic acceptorless dehydrogenation or transfer dehydrogenation. (a) Co(II)-catalyzed acceptorless dehydrogenation of primary alcohols.⁷⁵ (b) Ni(II)-catalyzed acceptorless dehydrogenation of primary alcohols.⁷⁶ (c) Ru(II)-catalyzed acceptorless dehydrogenation of primary alcohols.⁷⁷ (d) Dehydrogenative coupling (transfer dehydrogenation) for primary alcohol oxidation catalyzed by Rh(I) acetamido catalyst.⁷⁸

ods can harness molecular oxygen without metals: ethylene-bridged flavinium salts accomplished metal-free aerobic oxidation of benzylic substrates (toluene derivatives and benzyl alcohols) to benzoic acids under visible light.⁶⁰

Despite the surge of catalytic strategies in the laboratory, large-scale carboxylic acid production continues to rely on established aerobic O₂ routes. For instance, the AMOCO process, employing Co–Mn–Br catalysts for the liquid-phase oxidation of *p*-xylene via the corresponding primary alcohol, remains the industrial standard for terephthalic acid manufacturing, an essential platform chemical, e.g., as a monomer in polyester and PET production.⁶¹ Similarly, the industrial standard for benzoic acid synthesis is the Co-catalyzed aerobic oxidation of toluene via the alcohol intermediate, typically conducted in the liquid phase under elevated temperature and pressure.^{62,63} These processes underscore both the robustness and limitations of traditional autoxidation chemistry on a bulk scale. Both processes are highly efficient and scalable; however, they require harsh conditions, strong promoters, and specialized reactors to address selectivity and safety.

Electrochemical Oxidation

In recent years, electrochemical oxidation protocols have frequently been reported.^{64,65} In general, these methods

involve either a redox mediator that cycles between oxidation of the substrate and reductive recovery, or direct oxidation of primary alcohols occurring at the (activated) anode.

Ni-based (oxy)hydroxides [e.g., Ni(OH)₂ anodes] remain the most studied systems, which form the active Ni species upon activation by current. Mechanistic studies revealed two potential-dependent regimes, involving either hydrogen atom transfer (lower potentials) or hydride transfer at Ni(IV) centers (higher potentials).^{66,67} The structural state of NiOOH is decisive, with β -NiOOH (more stable, lower valence) promoting aldehyde formation, while γ -NiOOH (highly active, disordered, higher-valence state) and strongly alkaline conditions drive the complete oxidation to carboxylates.⁶⁸ The catalytic cycle is closed by the cathodic hydrogen evolution reaction.

Oxidation of primary alkyl, aryl, and allylic alcohols at Ni(OH)₂ anodes was reported as early as 1979, demonstrating that in alkaline solution, primary alcohols can be oxidized to carboxylic acids (Figure 6a).⁶⁹ Furthermore, mainly hetero-aromatic primary alcohols were oxidized by a Ni(OH)₂-coated anode to carboxylic acids in batch and flow with minimal Ni-leaching (Figure 6b).⁷⁰

Aminoxyl mediators such as TEMPO and 4-acetamido-TEMPO (ACT) allow milder and more functional-group-

Figure 8. Reactive species involved in the enzymatic oxidation of primary alcohols to carboxylic acids. (a) Oxidation of primary alcohols to carboxylic acids. (b) Alcohol dehydrogenase (e.g., ADH, PDB ID 1A4U) and aldehyde dehydrogenase (ALDH) catalyze oxidations using NAD(P)⁺ as the hydride acceptor.^{84,85} (c) Heme-containing enzymes such as CYP450s or unspecific peroxygenases (UPOs) catalyze primary alcohol oxidation via a compound I intermediate through a radical rebound mechanism (e.g., UPO, PDB ID 9J1Q).^{87,89,91} (d) Non-heme diiron monooxygenases catalyze oxidations via intermediate Q through a radical rebound-type mechanism (e.g., alkane monooxygenase, PDB ID 8F6T).⁹² (e) FAD-dependent oxidases catalyze oxidations by overall hydride abstraction, with FAD serving as the electron acceptor (e.g., choline oxidase, PDB ID 4MJW).⁹⁴ (f) Cu-radical oxidases catalyze oxidations by hydrogen atom abstraction through a tyrosyl-Cu(II) radical in a radical-type mechanism (e.g., galactose oxidase, PDB ID 1GOF).⁹⁹

tolerant oxidations toward carboxylic acids.^{71,72} In an ACT-mediated electrochemical oxidation, alcohols and aldehydes were converted to carboxylic acids (Figure 6c).⁷¹ This process was carried out at room temperature in aqueous buffer, releasing H₂ as the sole coproduct. A broad substrate scope and preserved stereochemical integrity were achieved, including gram-scale synthesis of a precursor of the pharmaceutical levetiracetam.

Both Ni(OH)₂-anodic and ACT-mediated electrochemical oxidation of primary alcohols represent efficient and sustainable alternatives to other conventional oxidants, offering high selectivity while generating H₂ as the sole byproduct. However, despite these advantages, their performance is closely tied to the electrode configuration and mass transport in aqueous media, which can pose challenges for scale-up.

Additionally, alternative methods were also investigated, but mostly remain niche. For instance, the “oxidation by reduction” concept employs cathodically activated persulfate to generate sulfate radicals that oxidize alcohols.⁷³ While effective, compared to true electrocatalysis, this method requires stoichiometric oxidants and produces more waste, limiting its sustainability. Furthermore, mixed oxides such as Co₂NiO₄ enable tuning the reaction selectivity, though the competing oxygen evolution reaction remains a limitation.⁷⁴

Dehydrogenation

Besides methods relying on external oxidants, conversion of primary alcohols to carboxylic acids can also be achieved via catalytic dehydrogenation, in which H₂ is released in an “acceptorless” option or by employing a sacrificial hydrogen acceptor.⁴

A broad spectrum of acceptorless dehydrogenation methods for the oxidation of primary alcohols has been developed,

especially in the field of homogeneous catalysis. For instance, Co(II) pincer complexes catalyze the oxidation of primary alcohols to carboxylate salts with H₂ as the only byproduct, while showing functional group tolerance and high yields (Figure 7a).⁷⁵ Comparably, Ni(II) N’NN’ pincer complexes catalyze acceptorless dehydrogenation of primary alcohols, resulting in 40–90% yield of the corresponding carboxylic acid (Figure 7b).⁷⁶ Ru(II) complexes with benzimidazole–pyridine pincers represent one of the most efficient homogeneous systems. In alcohol/CsOH medium, primary alcohols were formally oxidized to carboxylic acids in high yields with TONs reaching ~10,000 (Figure 7c).⁷⁷

A Rh(I)–amido complex, [Rh(trop₂N)(PPh₃)], was reported to enable the dehydrogenative coupling of primary alcohols in the presence of water to afford carboxylic acids (Figure 7d).⁷⁸ Although Rh(I)–amido-catalyzed dehydrogenative coupling enabled the mild, chemoselective oxidation of primary alcohols to the carboxylic acids with recyclable cyclohexanone/H₂O₂ as a hydrogen shuttle, its reliance on Rh, the air sensitivity, and the system complexity pose limits to its application.

From an applicative perspective, acceptorless dehydrogenation offers advantages such as not relying on oxidants, having H₂ as the sole coproduct, and a broad substrate spectrum across benzylic, aliphatic, and functionalized alcohols. However, these methods are often carried out under harsh reaction conditions (~150 °C, strong bases, and extended reaction times). Ru(II)-catalyzed systems often suffer from product precipitation, Ni(II)-catalyzed ones from low activity and etherification side reactions, and Co(II)-based approaches from high catalyst loadings and reduced efficiency for electron-poor substrates. Current moderate turnover numbers for bulk

Figure 9. Oxidation of primary alcohols with wild-type whole-cell biocatalysts. (a) Multistep oxidation of 1,3-diols catalyzed by fermenting cells of *Acetobacter aceti* MIM 2000/28.¹⁰⁵ (b) Multistep oxidation of 2-phenylethanol catalyzed by immobilized cells of *Gluconobacter oxydans* NCIMB 8035 under nongrowth conditions.¹⁰⁷ (c) Multistep oxidation of limonene catalyzed by fermenting cells of *Pseudomonas putida* GS1.¹⁰⁸ (d) Multistep oxidation of 1,2-diols catalyzed by cells of *Sphingomonas* sp. HXN-200 under nongrowth conditions.¹¹⁰

chemicals, operational challenges, as well as varying costs of the catalyst, e.g., Ru(II)-based methods, represent disadvantages.

■ BIOCATALYTIC OXIDATIONS

Although the oxidation of primary alcohols to carboxylic acids is still predominantly carried out using chemical methods, the rapid development of biocatalysis has opened new opportunities over the past decades.^{6,8–12} Biocatalysis, the use of enzymes to catalyze chemical transformations, enables precise reactivity control via finely tuned interactions in the active sites of enzymes. This allows high regio- and chemoselectivity, which minimizes or avoids side reactions. Biocatalysts typically operate in water as a solvent under ambient temperature and pressure, achieving high turnover frequencies (in general per second). Additionally, enzymes are produced from renewables and are biodegradable.

Nevertheless, biocatalysis, particularly when employing wild-type enzymes, still faces some challenges, including low to moderate substrate loadings, limited space-time yields, and moderate catalyst stability compared to chemical catalysts. To address these limitations, enzyme engineering is a powerful strategy for adapting enzymes to the desired reaction conditions.^{79–83} Typically, enzyme engineering in combination with process engineering enables efficient and scalable biocatalytic transformations.

Analogous to chemical oxidation methods, biocatalytic oxidation of primary alcohols to carboxylic acids proceeds via

two reaction steps with aldehydes and the corresponding hydrates as intermediates (Figure 8a). Both oxidation steps may be catalyzed by the same enzyme or by two different enzymes, each specialized either for the alcohol or the aldehyde oxidation step. Consequently, the reaction mechanisms differ depending on the type of enzyme used and the corresponding oxidant.

Alcohol or aldehyde dehydrogenases (ADH/AIDH) catalyzed oxidations involve a hydride transfer from the α -carbon of the substrate to the oxidized nicotinamide adenine dinucleotide cofactor, NAD(P)⁺ (Figure 8b).^{84,85} While AIDHs selectively catalyze the oxidation of aldehydes to acids via a monothioacetal intermediate covalently bound to an active site cysteine,⁸⁵ ADHs can perform either just the oxidation of the alcohol or both oxidation steps, thus alcohol oxidation and aldehyde oxidation, depending on the specific enzyme.⁸⁶

Heme-dependent enzymes rely on a highly reactive oxoferryl porphyrin π -cation radical (compound I, Figure 8c) as the reactive species, which is formed from the resting state of heme using molecular oxygen/electrons or hydrogen peroxide. While cytochrome P450 monooxygenases (CYP450) require molecular oxygen in combination with electron shuttling,^{87,88} peroxygenases shortcut the formation of compound I by using H₂O₂, thereby circumventing the need for electron shuttling and O₂.^{89–91} Compound I can abstract a hydrogen atom from the substrate, forming a carbon-centered substrate radical and an Fe(IV)–OH species. The latter subsequently

Figure 10. Oxidation of primary alcohols to the corresponding carboxylic acid using alcohol dehydrogenases (ADH, PDB ID 1A4U) and, in selected cases, simultaneously aldehyde dehydrogenases (AIDH, PDB ID 8YEN). (a) Simultaneous oxidation cascade catalyzed by the ADH PEDH and AIDH PADH. NAD⁺ was regenerated with NADH oxidase (NOX).¹¹⁶ (b) Oxidation cascade of 1,2-diols catalyzed by horse liver ADH (HLADH) and an AIDH. NAD⁺ was regenerated with glutamate dehydrogenase (GluDH).¹¹⁷ (c) Two-step oxidation catalyzed by a single ADH (HeADH-II).⁸⁶

transfers a hydroxyl radical to the substrate via a radical rebound, yielding the oxidized product.⁸⁸

Non-heme diiron monooxygenases coordinate two iron Fe(III) atoms in their active site. Upon reduction of the two Fe(III) to Fe(II), O₂ is bound; subsequent cleavage of the O–O bond leads to formation of the reactive Fe(IV)–Fe(IV)–O₂ diamond-core intermediate structure (intermediate Q) (Figure 8d). The reactive species abstracts a hydrogen atom from the substrate, followed by oxygen rebound, releasing the oxidized product.^{92,93}

Flavin-dependent oxidases bind flavin adenine dinucleotide (FAD) covalently or non-covalently in their active site (Figure 8e).^{94–98} Overall, a hydride is transferred from the substrate to the oxidized FAD cofactor, generating FADH₂, which is oxidized back to FAD at the expense of molecular oxygen, leading to H₂O₂ as a coproduct.

Copper oxidases catalyze the aerobic oxidation of primary alcohols to carboxylic acids via a coupled metal-radical mechanism (Figure 8f). In the Cu-dependent galactose oxidase, a mononuclear Cu center ligated by histidine residues together with a Cys–Tyr radical mediates the two-electron oxidation of alcohol or aldehyde substrates. At the Cu(I)

center, O₂ is activated and reduced to H₂O₂, thereby closing the catalytic cycle.^{95,96,99}

The biocatalytic methods are grouped here based on the stoichiometric oxidant (organic molecules, O₂, or H₂O₂), considering also the type of enzyme involved. Nevertheless, approaches using wild-type whole cells are discussed first.

Wild-Type Whole Cells

Historically, the biocatalytic oxidation of primary alcohols to carboxylic acids started with the use of wild-type whole-cell biocatalysts in the second half of the 20th century.^{100–102} In general, the methods rely on air or O₂-enriched air to provide molecular oxygen as an oxidant in sufficient quantity; however, also organic compounds like glucose or glycerol are required as reagents. Notably, the whole cells may be used either in a resting or fermenting state.

The most common microorganisms employed as whole-cell biocatalysts were acetic acid bacteria, such as *Acetobacter aceti*, which was used for the enantioselective synthesis of 2-phenylpropionic acid,¹⁰³ phenylacetic acid,¹⁰⁴ or the regio- and stereoselective oxidation of chiral 2-alkyl-1,3-diols to the corresponding chiral 2-hydroxymethyl alkanolic acids (Figure 9a).¹⁰⁵

Gluconobacter oxidans, another acetic acid bacterium, is frequently used for the oxidation of alcohols to carboxylic acids, such as to synthesize aliphatic acids with chain length between C4 and C7,¹⁰⁶ or D-(–)-lactic acid from racemic 1,2-propanediol. An interesting study demonstrated the oxidation of 2-phenylethanol to phenylacetic acid using immobilized *Gluconobacter oxidans*, which showed increased tolerance to 2-phenylethanol and a longer production time compared to free cells (Figure 9b).¹⁰⁷

Different strains of *Pseudomonas putida* have been employed in the selective sequential oxidation of limonene to perillonic acid, a relevant compound for the pharmaceutical industry, with product titers of up to 11 g/L (Figure 9c).^{108,109} *Pseudomonas putida* also catalyzes the oxidation of methyl groups on heteroarenes to yield heteroaromatic carboxylic acids. This reaction was scaled up to 1000 L, reaching product titers up to 24 g/L.¹⁰⁰ Other notable examples are the use of *Sphingomonas* sp. HXN-200 cells to catalyze the regio- and stereoselective oxidations of 3-*O*-benzylglycerol to the corresponding (*R*)-hydroxy carboxylic acid (Figure 9d),¹¹⁰ or *Corynebacterium* sp. catalyzing the oxidation of trimethylpropane to 2,2-bis(hydroxymethyl)butyric acid. Examples of whole-cell biocatalysts belonging to the fungal kingdom have also been reported, like the use of *Candida tropicalis* cells to convert *n*-alkanes to the corresponding α,ω -dicarboxylic acids.¹¹¹

Oxidation methods applying wild-type whole cells allow the conversion of several primary alcohols under mild conditions, exploiting the enzymes and cofactors already present within the wild-type catalyst. Low production cost of the biomass and the absence of GMO regulations for wild-type microorganisms represent advantages. In general, little prior knowledge of the biological system is required, making the process easy to implement; however, controlling the outcome is usually complex, as the whole metabolism is not optimized for exclusive alcohol oxidation. Consequently, side reactions, low to moderate substrate loadings, and mass transfer limitations through the cell membrane may be issues. Furthermore, the wild-type enzymes are typically expressed at low levels in native strains, and the substrate scope is usually narrow.

Dehydrogenases

Combining alcohol dehydrogenases (ADH) and aldehyde dehydrogenases (AIDH) in a cascade^{112–115} is commonly adopted for the oxidation of primary alcohols to the corresponding carboxylic acids (Figure 10). In contrast to the wild-type whole-cell approach, defined enzymes are utilized in cell-free systems or as whole-cell catalysts. Both the ADH and AIDH rely on the oxidized nicotinamide cofactors (NAD⁺ or NADP⁺), which are reduced during the oxidation of the alcohol and the aldehyde substrates. To avoid the use of stoichiometric amounts of NAD(P)⁺, regeneration systems are usually implemented. Depending on the cofactor regeneration system, the stoichiometric oxidant can be either O₂,¹¹⁶ or organic molecules, e.g., α -ketoglutarate (α -KG).¹¹⁷ Since ADHs catalyze alcohol oxidation and some ADHs also aldehyde oxidation, different cascade designs are feasible, e.g., utilizing a single ADH for both steps or combining an ADH with an AIDH.

An example of an ADH and AIDH cascade was reported, transforming aromatic and aliphatic alcohols to the corresponding acids using the NADH oxidase (NOX) for NAD⁺

recycling at the expense of O₂ and simultaneous formation of H₂O₂ (Figure 10a).¹¹⁶

In a similar cascade, the enantioselective oxidation of 1,2-diols to L- α -hydroxy acids was achieved using coimmobilized ADH and AIDH.¹¹⁷ In this case, the NAD⁺ regeneration was performed using a glutamate dehydrogenase, which converted α -ketoglutarate (α -KG) and ammonia to glutamate while consuming NADH (Figure 10b).

In a few cases, a single ADH catalyzed both steps, thus the sequential oxidation of alcohols to aldehyde and finally to carboxylic acid. For instance, the alcohol dehydrogenase HeADH-II catalyzed the oxidation of aromatic or alkyl alcohols, showing high tolerance toward polar solvents and high salt concentrations (Figure 10c).⁸⁶ Furthermore, a lanthanide-dependent ADH (PedH) performed several oxidative steps, converting hydroxymethylfurfural (HMF) to furandicarboxylic acid (FDCA).¹¹⁸ Interestingly, two ADHs were also combined for transforming 1, ω -diols. Here, the two ADHs catalyzed diol and lactol oxidation to form a lactone, which was finally hydrolyzed by a lactonase to yield the corresponding ω -hydroxy carboxylic acid (20 mM diol, up to 90% yield).¹¹⁹

The oxidation of HMF to FDCA was also performed in a cascade combining a galactose oxidase for alcohol oxidation using O₂ as oxidant (see the next section) and an ADH for aldehyde oxidation.¹²⁰ Interestingly, the NAD(P)⁺ cofactor regeneration was achieved through a horseradish peroxidase (HRP), which oxidized the reduced nicotinamide cofactor at the expense of hydrogen peroxide formed by the oxidase, thus scavenging this harmful oxidant that could otherwise cause enzyme inactivation.

Various studies showed the possibility of generating the primary alcohol in situ by hydroxylating alkanes and subsequently oxidizing the alcohol to the corresponding carboxylic acid using ADH and AIDH. For example, the synthesis of tulipalin A was achieved starting with the terminal hydroxylation of isoprenyl acetate mediated by the alkane monooxygenase AlkB, followed by the oxidation with an ADH and an AIDH.¹²¹ Similar examples used cytochrome P450 monooxygenases,^{122,123} non-heme diiron monooxygenases,¹²⁴ or unspecific peroxygenases¹²⁵ to catalyze the initial hydroxylation of the substrate to generate the primary alcohol.

Overall, dehydrogenases are widely available and well-established biocatalysts for the oxidation of primary alcohols to carboxylic acids. Heterologous expression in *Escherichia coli* is straightforward, and protein engineering is a powerful tool to improve their activity.¹¹⁸ The need of nicotinamide cofactors and their recycling make them more complex than some of the following options.^{116,120}

Monooxygenases and Oxidases

Another strategy to access carboxylic acids via a two-step biocatalytic oxidation of primary alcohols involves monooxygenases and oxidases, both utilizing molecular oxygen as a stoichiometric oxidant. Monooxygenases require O₂ and additionally a reducing equivalent, in general in the form of NAD(P)H, which is ideally recycled.^{88,126} While monooxygenases generate water as coproducts, oxidases produce hydrogen peroxide. Each class of enzyme can potentially catalyze the oxidation of the alcohol as well as the oxidation of the aldehyde hydrate.

For the electron transfer from NAD(P)H to the iron center of monooxygenases, a complex machinery is operating,

Figure 11. Two-step oxidation of primary alcohols to acids employing monooxygenases (cytochrome P450 monooxygenases, or nonheme diiron monooxygenases) or oxidases (PDB ID 4MJW) using O₂ as a stoichiometric oxidant. (a) Oxidation of 20-dihydrosamycin catalyzed by the CYP450 RosC coexpressed in whole cells (*E. coli*).¹³⁷ (b) Oxidation of *n*-alkanes catalyzed by the non-heme diiron monooxygenase AlkB (using whole *E. coli* cells).¹⁴⁰ (c) Multistep oxidation of 1,ω-diol and 1-hexanol to carboxylic acids catalyzed by the FAD-dependent alcohol oxidase.¹⁴⁷ (d) Multistep oxidation of primary alcohols catalyzed by the engineered Cu-dependent oxidase Goase M₃₋₅.¹⁴⁸

involving, for instance, electron carrier proteins like ferredoxin, ferredoxin reductases, or cytochrome P450 reductases.¹²⁷ Due to this complexity and the need for a reducing agent to recycle the NAD(P)H, sacrificial electron donors are usually added, such as sugars and other carbohydrates (e.g., glycerol) for whole-cell systems.^{128,129} Nevertheless, stoichiometric amounts of nicotinamide cofactors in the case of cell-free biocatalysis have also been described.¹³⁰ Due to this complexity, whole-cell biocatalysts are the preferred format for this approach, since the monooxygenase and the electron carrier proteins are simultaneously expressed in a heterologous host.^{131,132}

Two classes of monooxygenases were identified as capable of catalyzing the reaction of interest: cytochrome P450 monooxygenases (CYP450s), which use a heme prosthetic group, and non-heme diiron monooxygenases, which feature two iron atoms in their active site. CYP450s were employed in several studies, such as the *in vitro* conversion of ethanol to acetic acid by CYP2E1,¹³⁰ or the 3-step oxidation of sterols by the sterol-27-hydroxylase (a mitochondrial CYP450) expressed in mammalian cells.¹³³

In other cases, plant CYP450s, like CYP94A5, were expressed in yeast, which catalyzed the terminal oxidation of

fatty acids to dicarboxylic acids,¹³⁴ or CYP71AV1, used to synthesize the antimalarial drug precursor artemisinin acid starting from the sesquiterpene amorpha-4,11-diene.¹³⁵ Bacteria belonging to the actinomycetes are an important source of CYP450s, of which many are involved in the biosynthesis of natural products.¹³⁶ For instance, the CYP450 RosC was coexpressed in *E. coli* together with the electron carrier proteins CamA (putidaredoxin) and CamB (putidaredoxin reductase). The whole-cell catalyst catalyzed the multistep oxidation of 20-dihydrosamycin to 20-carboxyrosamicin (Figure 11a).¹³⁷

The following synthetic applications to access carboxylic acids involve non-heme diiron enzymes. The multistep oxidation of toluenes or xylenes was catalyzed by xylene monooxygenase (XylM) expressed in *E. coli* together with the reductase XylA,¹³⁸ while the conversion of alkanes to mono or dicarboxylic acids was enabled by AlkB, coexpressed in *E. coli* with AlkG and AlkT as electron carrier proteins (Figure 11b).^{139,140}

Oxidases are stand-alone enzymes requiring molecular oxygen for their activity and generating hydrogen peroxide as a coproduct.^{97,98,141–143} Consequently, catalases are often

Figure 12. Oxidation of primary alcohols with heme-containing enzymes, including unspecific peroxygenases (UPOs, PDB ID 9J1Q) or cytochrome P450 monooxygenases in peroxygenase mode using H_2O_2 as a stoichiometric oxidant. (a) Multistep oxidation of HMF catalyzed by *Mor*UPO and *Aae*UPO in a two-step, one-pot reaction.¹⁵³ (b) Multistep oxidation of toluene derivatives catalyzed by *rAae*UPO-PaDa-I-H.¹⁵⁴ (c) Multistep oxidation of toluene derivatives catalyzed by *Tte*UPO fused with the formate oxidase AoFO_x.⁸³ (d) Multistep oxidation of 4-*tert*-butylbenzoic acid catalyzed by engineered CYP199A4 in peroxygenase mode.¹⁵⁵

added to disproportionate the harmful peroxide into water and O_2 .¹⁴⁴

Among flavin-dependent oxidases, hydroxymethylfurfural oxidase (HMFO) was used to catalyze the multistep oxidation of HMF (5 mM) to the corresponding dicarboxylic acid FDCA (95% product, TON: 570).¹⁴⁵ Moreover, rational engineering of the active site of HMFO enhanced the oxidation of aldehyde intermediates, allowing the conversion of several substituted benzylic alcohols to the corresponding acids, albeit with a low percentage of acid formation.¹⁴⁶ Another example is the alcohol oxidase AOX from *Phanerochaete chrysosporium*, which catalyzes the multistep oxidation of aliphatic primary alcohols and 1, ω -diols to the corresponding acids and hydroxyacids or oxa acids, respectively, with a TON of up to 1500 (Figure 11c).¹⁴⁷ Furthermore, the choline oxidase, also flavin-dependent, was engineered to increase its thermal and solvent stability, as well as the substrate scope, leading preferentially to the aldehyde.⁸² Nevertheless, overoxidation was observed for cinnamyl alcohol to the corresponding acid at 20% conversion.

In addition to flavin-dependent oxidases, the galactose oxidase GOase is a copper-dependent enzyme, which was

engineered (Goase M₃₋₅ mutant) to oxidize different substituted benzylic and heteroaromatic benzylic alcohols (Figure 11d).¹⁴⁸ Furthermore, the Goase M₃₋₅ variant was also used in cascades combined with either a xanthine dehydrogenase (a flavin-dependent oxidase),¹⁴⁹ or the aldehyde oxidase PaoAC, to achieve the conversion of HMF to FDCA, as well as several aliphatic and aromatic alcohols to the corresponding acids.¹⁵⁰

Transformations with monooxygenases are, in general, considered challenging due to the complexity of the electron transfer system. At a first glance, oxidases seem to be a highly interesting option, but substrate loadings are still low, as well as turnover numbers. As only a few examples have been published until now, progress may be expected in the future.

Peroxygenases

Since their discovery in 2004,¹⁵¹ unspecific peroxygenases (UPOs), being heme-dependent enzymes, have gained increasing attention due to their ability to efficiently accept H_2O_2 as oxidant as well as to their broad substrate scope. Furthermore, UPOs show impressive stability in the presence

of H₂O₂, making them a more viable option compared to O₂/NAD(P)H-dependent P450s.^{152,90} Consequently, unlike CYP450s, peroxygenases do not need additional proteins to shuttle electrons or sacrificial electron donors. UPOs have been used for the sequential oxidation of HMF to FDCA catalyzed by *Mor*UPO and *Aae*UPO, in a two-step one-pot process, achieving 95% conversion of 100 mM substrate (Figure 12a).¹⁵³ Due to high substrate loading and the low enzyme concentration, TONs reached up to 13500.

A single UPO, namely the PaDa-I variant of the UPO from *Agroclybe aegerita* (*rAae*UPO-PaDa-I-H), was used to catalyze the oxidation of the terpenoid 3-carene to chaminic acid,¹⁵⁶ and of different toluenes and benzylic alcohols to the corresponding acids (Figure 12b).¹⁵⁴ The same enzyme also showed the ability to oxidize (*E*)-allylic alcohols selectively from an *E/Z* mixture to the carboxylic acid/aldehyde products, respectively.¹⁵⁷

A fusion protein of *Tte*UPO with the formate oxidase AoFOx was used for the oxidation of toluene derivatives, yielding the corresponding carboxylic acids. In this approach, the H₂O₂ required for the activity of *Tte*UPO was generated in situ via the oxidation of formate catalyzed by the formate oxidase. Furthermore, H₂O₂ was also provided externally by slow addition for increasing product formation (Figure 12c).⁸³

Nevertheless, among heme-dependent enzymes, not only UPOs, but also a few CYP450s were reported to have peroxygenase activity.^{158–160} This feature was observed with CYP199A4, which was engineered to further increase its peroxygenase activity and used to perform the multistep oxidation of 4-*tert*-butylbenzoic acid to a dicarboxylic acid (Figure 12d).¹⁵⁵

Despite the encouraging advances in UPO-catalyzed oxidations, their applicability still faces some challenges. For instance, the heterologous expression is often poor or not yet feasible in conventional bacterial systems like *E. coli*.^{90,161} This issue is usually solved by using yeast (e.g., *Komagataella phaffii*) as a heterologous expression host, which excretes the enzymes into the medium, allowing straightforward enzyme isolation.⁹⁰ Furthermore, UPOs are, like any enzyme, prone to deactivation by H₂O₂. To avoid/minimize degradation, the reactive oxidant is either generated in situ,^{144,162,163} or constantly fed to keep its concentration at a tolerated level.^{153,164}

FUTURE PERSPECTIVES

The perspective shows that oxidation methods to transform primary alcohols to the corresponding carboxylic acids have evolved over time. The field has progressed from “brute force” methods relying on metalates in (over)stoichiometric amounts over noncharacterized whole-cell oxidations, to finely tuned catalytic approaches, utilizing environmentally benign oxidants such as H₂O₂ or molecular oxygen. This development can be observed for both chemical catalysts and biocatalysts. While dehydrogenation methods have been frequently reported for chemical systems, this has not been shown for biocatalysts, yet. However, recent research¹⁶⁵ suggests that biocatalytic transfer-dehydrogenation of alcohols to acids could be realized by exploiting, for instance, a hydrogenase that recycles NAD⁺ from NADH, releasing H₂ as the sole byproduct. Similarly, the oxidation of alcohols to acids has been performed using electrochemical methods, but comparable enzymatic strategies remain undeveloped, although they appear feasible based on advances in related biocatalytic reactions.^{166–168}

Considering the reported data for the oxidation of primary alcohols to the corresponding acids, chemical catalysts show turnover numbers mostly in the range of 100, sometimes reaching up to 10000. Comparable performance has been observed for the enzymatic approaches, where TONs up to 13500 were reached for the oxidation of alcohols to acids employing UPOs.¹⁵³ In general, the trend is heading toward methods with low environmental impact, which is expected to go hand in hand with reduced costs. The simpler the reagent (O₂, H₂O₂, or even no oxidant in case of dehydrogenation), the fewer coproducts are formed, and the less waste needs to be considered. Factors such as the amount and the type of solvent, reaction temperature, and the catalyst also influence the overall environmental footprint. To reduce process costs and enhance recyclability and biodegradability, catalysts should be readily manufactured from renewable sources, exhibit high stability, and deliver high total turnover numbers (TTN), thus the TON during the lifetime of the catalyst. While for pharma products TONs of 4000 are acceptable, specialty chemicals require a TON of around 80,000.^{13,169} Future advances will particularly depend on increasing the turnover numbers (TON) for all types of catalysts, accompanied by improving stability and activity; for enzyme, e.g., via protein engineering or de novo enzyme design.^{79–83} Furthermore, to reach high space-time yields an elevated substrate concentration is important. Chemical methods usually operate at higher substrate concentrations (>100 mM) compared to biocatalytic methods, which need to be improved in the future to reach competitive substrate loadings of at least 50–100 mM.

AUTHOR INFORMATION

Corresponding Author

Wolfgang Kroutil – Austrian Centre of Industrial Biotechnology, Institute of Chemistry, University of Graz, 8010 Graz, Austria; Institute of Chemistry, University of Graz, 8010 Graz, Austria; Field of Excellence BioHealth, BioTechMed Graz, Cluster of Excellence Circular Bioengineering, University of Graz, 8010 Graz, Austria; orcid.org/0000-0002-2151-6394; Email: wolfgang.kroutil@uni-graz.at

Authors

Jonas Spang – Austrian Centre of Industrial Biotechnology, Institute of Chemistry, University of Graz, 8010 Graz, Austria; orcid.org/0009-0007-9888-077X
Francesco Mascia – Austrian Centre of Industrial Biotechnology, Institute of Chemistry, University of Graz, 8010 Graz, Austria

Complete contact information is available at:
<https://pubs.acs.org/10.1021/jacsau.Sc01452>

Author Contributions

†J.S. and F.M. contributed equally. CRediT: **Jonas Spang** conceptualization, writing - original draft, writing - review & editing; **Francesco Mascia** conceptualization, writing - original draft, writing - review & editing; **Wolfgang Kroutil** conceptualization, funding acquisition, project administration, resources, supervision, writing - review & editing.

Funding

The COMET center acib: Next Generation Bioproduction is funded by BMK, BMAW, SFG, Standortagentur Tirol,

Government of Lower Austria, and Vienna Business Agency in the framework of Competence Centers for Excellent Technologies (COMET). The COMET Funding Program is managed by the Austrian Research Promotion Agency FFG, the Austrian Science Fund (FWF) (10.55776/COE17 within the Cluster of Excellence Circular Bioengineering), and the University of Graz and the Field of Excellence BioHealth.

Notes

The authors declare no competing financial interest.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The University of Graz and the Field of Excellence BioHealth are acknowledged for financial support. W.K. acknowledges the Austrian Science Fund (FWF) for funding the Cluster of Excellence Circular Bioengineering (CoE) and the Innovative Health Initiative Joint Undertaking (IHI JU) under grant agreement no 101165889. This research was funded in whole, or in part by the Austrian Science Fund (FWF) [10.55776/COE17]. For the purpose of open access, the author has applied a CC BY public copyright licence to any Author Accepted Manuscript version arising from this submission. The JU receives support from the European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme and COCIR, EFPIA, Europa Bio, MedTech Europe, and Vaccines Europe.

ABBREVIATIONS

α -KG, α -ketoglutaric acid; ABTS, 2,2'-azinobis(3-ethylbenzothiazoline-6-sulfonic acid); ACT, 4-acetamido-TEMPO; ADH, alcohol dehydrogenase; AIDH, aldehyde dehydrogenase; CYP450, cytochrome P450 monooxygenase; DCE, 1,2-dichloroethane; eq. or equiv, equivalents; DMF, dimethylformamide; FADH₂, flavin adenine dinucleotide, reduced form; FDCA, furandicarboxylic acid; GMO, genetically modified organism; GMP, Good Manufacturing Practice; HMF, hydroxymethylfurfural; HRP, horseradish peroxidase; LED, light-emitting diode; NAD(P)H, nicotinamide dinucleotide (phosphate); NMO, *N*-methylmorpholine *N*-oxide; NOX, NADH oxidase; NSAID, nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drug; PDB, Protein Data Bank; PDC, pyridinium dichromate; PET, polyethylene terephthalate; PTC, phase transfer catalyst; Salen, *N,N'*-bis(salicylidene)ethylenediamine; TEMPO, 2,2,6,6-tetramethylpiperidin-1-oxyl; TON, turnover number; TPAP, tetra-*n*-propylammonium perruthenate; TPPT, 2,4,6-triphenylpyrylium tetrafluoroborate; TTN, total turnover number; UPO, unspecific peroxygenase; ΔG , Gibbs free energy change

REFERENCES

- (1) Kalgutkar, A. S.; Daniels, J. S. Chapter 3. Carboxylic Acids and their Bioisosteres. *Metabolism, Pharmacokinetics and Toxicity of Functional Groups: Impact of the Building Blocks of Medicinal Chemistry on ADMET*; Smith, D. A., Ed.; Royal Society of Chemistry, 2010; pp 99–167.
- (2) Dugger, R. W.; Ragan, J. A.; Ripin, D. H. B. Survey of GMP Bulk Reactions Run in a Research Facility between 1985 and 2002. *Org. Process Res. Dev.* **2005**, *9*, 253–258.
- (3) Tojo, G.; Fernández, M. *Oxidation of Primary Alcohols to Carboxylic Acids*; Springer: New York, 2007; DOI: 10.1007/0-387-35432-8.
- (4) Williams, T. J.; Cherepakhin, V. Direct Oxidation of Primary Alcohols to Carboxylic Acids. *Synthesis* **2021**, *53*, 1023–1034.

- (5) Bayer, T.; Wu, S.; Snajdrova, R.; Baldenius, K.; Bornscheuer, U. T. An Update: Enzymatic Synthesis for Industrial Applications. *Angew. Chem., Int. Ed.* **2025**, *64*, No. e202505976.
- (6) Kissman, E. N.; Sosa, M. B.; Millar, D. C.; Koleski, E. J.; Thevasundaram, K.; Chang, M. C. Y. Expanding chemistry through in vitro and in vivo biocatalysis. *Nature* **2024**, *631*, 37–48.
- (7) Jain, S.; Ospina, F.; Hammer, S. C. A New Age of Biocatalysis Enabled by Generic Activation Modes. *JACS Au* **2024**, *4*, 2068–2080.
- (8) France, S. P.; Lewis, R. D.; Martinez, C. A. The Evolving Nature of Biocatalysis in Pharmaceutical Research and Development. *JACS Au* **2023**, *3*, 715–735.
- (9) Romero, E. O.; Saucedo, A. T.; Hernández-Meléndez, J. R.; Yang, D.; Chakrabarty, S.; Narayan, A. R. H. Enabling Broader Adoption of Biocatalysis in Organic Chemistry. *JACS Au* **2023**, *3*, 2073–2085.
- (10) Buller, R.; Lutz, S.; Kazlauskas, R. J.; Snajdrova, R.; Moore, J. C.; Bornscheuer, U. T. From nature to industry: Harnessing enzymes for biocatalysis. *Science* **2023**, *382*, No. eadh8615.
- (11) Simic, S.; Zukic, E.; Schmermund, L.; Faber, K.; Winkler, C. K.; Kroutil, W. Shortening Synthetic Routes to Small Molecule Active Pharmaceutical Ingredients Employing Biocatalytic Methods. *Chem. Rev.* **2022**, *122*, 1052–1126.
- (12) Winkler, C. K.; Schrittwieser, J. H.; Kroutil, W. Power of Biocatalysis for Organic Synthesis. *ACS Cent. Sci.* **2021**, *7*, 55–71.
- (13) Dong, J.; Fernandez-Fueyo, E.; Hollmann, F.; Paul, C. E.; Pesic, M.; Schmidt, S.; Wang, Y.; Younes, S.; Zhang, W. Biocatalytic Oxidation Reactions: A Chemist's Perspective. *Angew. Chem., Int. Ed.* **2018**, *57*, 9238–9261.
- (14) Kroutil, W.; Mang, H.; Edegger, K.; Faber, K. Biocatalytic Oxidation of Primary and Secondary Alcohols. *Adv. Synth. Catal.* **2004**, *346*, 125–142.
- (15) Reid, E. E.; Worthington, H.; Larchar, A. W. The Action of Caustic Alkali and of Alkaline Salts on Alcohols. *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **1939**, *61*, 99–101.
- (16) Bowden, K.; Heilbron, I. M.; Jones, E. R. H.; Weedon, B. C. L. 13. Researches on acetylenic compounds. Part I. The preparation of acetylenic ketones by oxidation of acetylenic carbinols and glycols. *J. Chem. Soc.* **1946**, 39.
- (17) Wiberg, K. B.; Schafer, H. Direct Observation of Intermediates in the Chromic Acid Oxidation of Secondary Alcohols. *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **1967**, *89*, 455–457.
- (18) Holloway, F.; Cohen, M.; Westheimer, F. H. The Mechanism of the Chromic Acid Oxidation of Isopropyl Alcohol. The Chromic Acid Ester. *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **1951**, *73*, 65–68.
- (19) Acheson, R. M.; Verlander, M. S. Addition reactions of heterocyclic compounds. Part XL. Methyl propiolate with some quinolines, isoquinolines, and phenanthridines. *J. Chem. Soc. C* **1969**, 2311–2315.
- (20) Spino, C.; Gobdout, C. A stereodivergent approach to chiral nonracemic *N*-protected α,α -dialkylated amino acids. *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2003**, *125*, 12106–12107.
- (21) Corey, E. J.; Schmidt, G. Useful procedures for the oxidation of alcohols involving pyridinium dichromate in aprotic media. *Tetrahedron Lett.* **1979**, *20*, 399–402.
- (22) Takahashi, S.; Souma, K.; Hashimoto, R.; Koshino, H.; Nakata, T. Synthetic studies on macroviracin A: a rapid construction of C(42) macrocyclic dilactone corresponding to the core. *J. Org. Chem.* **2004**, *69*, 4509–4515.
- (23) Ciufolini, M. A.; Swaminathan, S. Synthesis of a model depsipeptide segment of Luzopeptins (BBM 928), potent antitumor and antiretroviral antibiotics. *Tetrahedron Lett.* **1989**, *30*, 3027–3028.
- (24) Lee, D. G.; Chen, T. The oxidation of alcohols by permanganate. A comparison with other high-valent transition-metal oxidants. *J. Org. Chem.* **1991**, *56*, 5341–5345.
- (25) Crombie, L.; Harper, S. H. 515. Synthesis and configuration of (+)-6-methyloctanoic acid, a degradation product of the polymyxins. *J. Chem. Soc.* **1950**, 2685–2689.
- (26) Dash, S.; Patel, S.; Mishra, B. K. Oxidation by permanganate: synthetic and mechanistic aspects. *Tetrahedron* **2009**, *65*, 707–739.

- (27) ten Brink, G. J.; Arends, I. W.; Sheldon, R. A. Green, catalytic oxidation of alcohols in water. *Science* **2000**, *287*, 1636–1639.
- (28) Caron, S.; Dugger, R. W.; Ruggeri, S. G.; Ragan, J. A.; Ripin, D. H. Large-scale oxidations in the pharmaceutical industry. *Chem. Rev.* **2006**, *106*, 2943–2989.
- (29) Zhao, M.; Li, J.; Song, Z.; Desmond, R.; Tschaen, D. M.; Grabowski, E. J. J.; Reider, P. J. A novel chromium trioxide catalyzed oxidation of primary alcohols to the carboxylic acids. *Tetrahedron Lett.* **1998**, *39*, 5323–5326.
- (30) Langer, P. Tetra-*n*-propyl Ammonium Perruthenate (TPAP)—An Efficient and Selective Reagent for Oxidation Reactions in Solution and on the Solid Phase. *J. Prakt. Chem.* **2000**, *342*, 728–730.
- (31) Schmidt, A. K.; Stark, C. B. TPAP-catalyzed direct oxidation of primary alcohols to carboxylic acids through stabilized aldehyde hydrates. *Org. Lett.* **2011**, *13*, 4164–4167.
- (32) Osato, H.; Kabaki, M.; Shimizu, S. Development of Safe, Scalable Nitric Acid Oxidation Using a Catalytic Amount of NaNO₂ for 3-Bromo-2,2-bis(bromomethyl)propanoic Acid: An Intermediate of S-013420. *Org. Process Res. Dev.* **2011**, *15*, 581–584.
- (33) Mondanaro, K. R.; Dailey, W. P. 3-Chloro-2-(chloromethyl)-1-propene. *Org. Synth.* **1998**, *75*, 89–97.
- (34) Mannam, S.; Sekar, G. CuCl catalyzed selective oxidation of primary alcohols to carboxylic acids with tert-butyl hydroperoxide at room temperature. *Tetrahedron Lett.* **2008**, *49*, 2457–2460.
- (35) Lucio Anelli, P.; Biffi, C.; Montanari, F.; Quici, S. Fast and selective oxidation of primary alcohols to aldehydes or to carboxylic acids and of secondary alcohols to ketones mediated by oxoammonium salts under two-phase conditions. *J. Org. Chem.* **1987**, *52*, 2559–2562.
- (36) Zanka, A. A simple and highly practical oxidation of primary alcohols to acids mediated by 2,2,6,6-tetramethyl-1-piperidinyloxy (TEMPO). *Chem. Pharm. Bull.* **2003**, *51*, 888–889.
- (37) Troiano, D.; Orsat, V.; Dumont, M.-J. Status of Biocatalysis in the Production of 2,5-Furandicarboxylic Acid. *ACS Catal.* **2020**, *10*, 9145–9169.
- (38) Luo, J.; Zhang, C.; Liu, W.; Li, Y.; Xie, B.; Zhang, J. Synthesis of a sustainable and robust heterogeneous TEMPO catalyst utilizing activated carbon for aerobic alcohol oxidation. *React. Chem. Eng.* **2024**, *9*, 1444–1451.
- (39) Giraldo Isaza, L.; Mortha, G.; Marlin, N.; Molton, F.; Duboc, C. ClO₂-Mediated Oxidation of the TEMPO Radical: Fundamental Considerations of the Catalytic System for the Oxidation of Cellulose Fibers. *Molecules* **2023**, *28*, No. 6631.
- (40) Ciriminna, R.; Albanese, L.; Meneguzzo, F.; Pagliaro, M. Hydrogen Peroxide: A Key Chemical for Today's Sustainable Development. *ChemSusChem* **2016**, *9*, 3374–3381.
- (41) Sato, K.; Aoki, M.; Takagi, J.; Noyori, R. Organic Solvent- and Halide-Free Oxidation of Alcohols with Aqueous Hydrogen Peroxide. *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **1997**, *119*, 12386–12387.
- (42) Das, S.; Punniyamurthy, T. Cobalt(II)-catalyzed oxidation of alcohols into carboxylic acids and ketones with hydrogen peroxide. *Tetrahedron Lett.* **2003**, *44*, 6033–6035.
- (43) Kon, Y.; Nakashima, T.; Makino, Y.; Onozawa, S. Y.; Miyamura, H.; Kobayashi, S.; Sato, K. Continuous-flow synthesis of carboxylic acids from alcohols via platinum and silicon dioxide-catalyzed hydrogen peroxide oxidation. *Org. Biomol. Chem.* **2025**, *23*, 2125–2132.
- (44) Mahmoudi, B.; Kazemnejadi, M. Ecofriendly metal-free olefins epoxidation and alcohol oxidation by in situ generated poly(peroxybenzoic acid) as a heterogeneous recyclable catalyst under mild conditions: an in-depth mechanistic study. *RSC Adv.* **2025**, *15*, 6110–6121.
- (45) Li, H.; Cao, L.; Yang, C.; Zhang, Z.; Zhang, B.; Deng, K. Selective oxidation of benzyl alcohols to benzoic acid catalyzed by eco-friendly cobalt thioporphyrine catalyst supported on silica-coated magnetic nanospheres. *J. Environ. Sci.* **2017**, *60*, 84–90.
- (46) Kasprzyk, W.; Galica, M.; Bednarz, S.; Bogdał, D. Microwave-Assisted Oxidation of Alcohols Using Zinc Polyoxometalate. *Synlett* **2014**, *25*, 2757–2760.
- (47) Liu, M.; Yu, F.; Yuan, B.; Xie, C.; Yu, S. Oxidation of 1-propanol to propionic acid with hydrogen peroxide catalyzed by heteropolyoxometalates. *BMC Chem.* **2021**, *15*, No. 23.
- (48) You, B.; Cheng, Z.; Tian, Y.; Wang, S.; Wang, B. Highly Efficient and Selective Oxidation of Benzyl Alcohol by WO₄²⁻ Catalyst Immobilized by a Phosphonium-Containing Porous Aromatic Framework. *Catalysts* **2023**, *13*, No. 1309.
- (49) Peer, M.; Weeranoppanant, N.; Adamo, A.; Zhang, Y.; Jensen, K. F. Biphasic Catalytic Hydrogen Peroxide Oxidation of Alcohols in Flow: Scale-up and Extraction. *Org. Process Res. Dev.* **2016**, *20*, 1677–1685.
- (50) Zhu, R.; Zhou, Y.-B.; Zhou, H.-Q.; Liu, F.-F. The Application of Peroxide for Organic Synthesis in Continuous Flow Chemistry. *Pharm. Fronts* **2023**, *05*, e243–e253.
- (51) Wang, C.; Xiao, J. Activation of Molecular Oxygen and Selective Oxidation with Metal Complexes. *Acc. Chem. Res.* **2025**, *58*, 714–731.
- (52) Grün, A. Die Oxydation von Paraffin. *Ber. Dtsch. Chem. Ges.* **1920**, *53*, 987–996.
- (53) Jiang, X.; Zhang, J.; Ma, S. Iron Catalysis for Room-Temperature Aerobic Oxidation of Alcohols to Carboxylic Acids. *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2016**, *138*, 8344–8347.
- (54) Yu, Y.; Zhai, D.; Zhou, Z.; Jiang, S.; Qian, H.; Ma, S. Copper-catalyzed aerobic oxidation of primary alcohols to carboxylic acids. *Chem. Commun.* **2023**, *59*, 5281–5284.
- (55) Fabbrini, M.; Galli, C.; Gentili, P.; Macchitella, D. An oxidation of alcohols by oxygen with the enzyme laccase and mediation by TEMPO. *Tetrahedron Lett.* **2001**, *42*, 7551–7553.
- (56) Cheng, A. D.; Zong, M. H.; Lu, G. H.; Li, N. Solvent-Promoted Oxidation of Aromatic Alcohols/Aldehydes to Carboxylic Acids by a Laccase-TEMPO System: Efficient Access to 2,5-Furandicarboxylic Acid and 5-Methyl-2-pyrazinecarboxylic Acid. *Adv. Sustainable Syst.* **2021**, *5*, No. 2000297.
- (57) Ahmed, M. S.; Mannel, D. S.; Root, T. W.; Stahl, S. S. Aerobic Oxidation of Diverse Primary Alcohols to Carboxylic Acids with a Heterogeneous Pd–Bi–Te/C (PBT/C) Catalyst. *Org. Process Res. Dev.* **2017**, *21*, 1388–1393.
- (58) Tambe, S. D.; Cho, E. J. Organophotocatalytic oxidation of alcohols to carboxylic acids. *Bull. Korean Chem. Soc.* **2022**, *43*, 1226–1230.
- (59) Zhou, L.; Chen, M.; Wang, Y.; Su, Y.; Yang, X.; Chen, C.; Xu, J. Au/mesoporous-TiO₂ as catalyst for the oxidation of alcohols to carboxylic acids with molecular oxygen in water. *Appl. Catal., A* **2014**, *475*, 347–354.
- (60) Zelenka, J.; Svobodova, E.; Tarabek, J.; Hoskovcova, I.; Boguschova, V.; Bailly, S.; Sikorski, M.; Roithova, J.; Cibulka, R. Combining Flavin Photocatalysis and Organocatalysis: Metal-Free Aerobic Oxidation of Unactivated Benzylic Substrates. *Org. Lett.* **2019**, *21*, 114–119.
- (61) Tomás, R. A. F.; Bordado, J. C. M.; Gomes, J. F. P.; Sheehan, R. J. Terephthalic Acid, Dimethyl Terephthalate, and Isophthalic Acid. In *Ullmann's Encyclopedia of Industrial Chemistry*; Wiley-VCH, 2024. DOI: 10.1002/14356007.a26_193.pub3.
- (62) Tang, Liang, B. Kinetics of the Liquid-Phase Oxidation of Toluene by Air. *Ind. Eng. Chem. Res.* **2007**, *46*, 6442–6448.
- (63) Gizli, A.; Aytimur, G.; Alpaya, E.; Atalay, S. Catalytic Liquid Phase Oxidation of Toluene to Benzoic Acid. *Chem. Eng. Technol.* **2008**, *31*, 409–416.
- (64) Li, K.; Ren, L.; Li, S.; Liu, L.; He, J.; Xu, Y.; Wang, M.; Zhao, S.; Wang, Y.; Chen, Y.; et al. Boosting electrocatalytic oxidation of heterocyclic alcohols with low usage aminoxyl radicals via MOF-derived NiOOH. *AlChE J.* **2024**, *70*, No. e18531.
- (65) Vitulano, F.; Solida, A.; Sorti, L.; Morelli, C. F.; Minguzzi, A.; Vertova, A. Alcohol and Carbonyl Redox Reactions in Electrochemical Organic Synthesis. *ChemistryEurope* **2025**, *3*, No. e202500013.
- (66) Bender, M. T.; Lam, Y. C.; Hammes-Schiffer, S.; Choi, K. S. Unraveling Two Pathways for Electrochemical Alcohol and Aldehyde Oxidation on NiOOH. *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2020**, *142*, 21538–21547.

- (67) Bender, M. T.; Warburton, R. E.; Hammes-Schiffer, S.; Choi, K.-S. Understanding Hydrogen Atom and Hydride Transfer Processes during Electrochemical Alcohol and Aldehyde Oxidation. *ACS Catal.* **2021**, *11*, 15110–15124.
- (68) Laan, P. C. M.; de Zwart, F. J.; Wilson, E. M.; Troglia, A.; Lugier, O. C. M.; Geels, N. J.; Bliem, R.; Reek, J. N. H.; de Bruin, B.; Rothenberg, G.; et al. Understanding the Oxidative Properties of Nickel Oxyhydroxide in Alcohol Oxidation Reactions. *ACS Catal.* **2023**, *13*, 8467–8476.
- (69) Kaulen, J.; Schäfer, H. J. Oxidation of Primary Alcohols to Carboxylic Acids at the Nickel Hydroxide Electrode. *Synthesis* **1979**, *1979*, 513–516.
- (70) Jud, W.; Salazar, C. A.; Imbrogno, J.; Verghese, J.; Guinness, S. M.; Desrosiers, J.-N.; Kappe, C. O.; Cantillo, D. Electrochemical Oxidation of Alcohols Using Nickel Oxide Hydroxide as Heterogeneous Electrocatalyst in Batch and Continuous Flow. *Org. Process Res. Dev.* **2022**, *26*, 1486–1495.
- (71) Rafiee, M.; Konz, Z. M.; Graaf, M. D.; Koolman, H. F.; Stahl, S. S. Electrochemical Oxidation of Alcohols and Aldehydes to Carboxylic Acids Catalyzed by 4-Acetamido-TEMPO: An Alternative to “Anelli” and “Pinnick” Oxidations. *ACS Catal.* **2018**, *8*, 6738–6744.
- (72) Rafiee, M.; Alherech, M.; Karlen, S. D.; Stahl, S. S. Electrochemical Aminoxyl-Mediated Oxidation of Primary Alcohols in Lignin to Carboxylic Acids: Polymer Modification and Depolymerization. *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2019**, *141*, 15266–15276.
- (73) Hosseini, S.; Janusz, J. N.; Tanwar, M.; Pendergast, A. D.; Neurock, M.; White, H. S. Oxidation by Reduction: Efficient and Selective Oxidation of Alcohols by the Electrocatalytic Reduction of Peroxydisulfate. *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2022**, *144*, 21103–21115.
- (74) Michaud, S. E.; Barber, M. M.; Rivera Cruz, K. E.; McCrory, C. C. L. Electrochemical Oxidation of Primary Alcohols Using a Co₂NiO₄ Catalyst: Effects of Alcohol Identity and Electrochemical Bias on Product Distribution. *ACS Catal.* **2023**, *13*, 515–529.
- (75) Pradhan, D. R.; Pattanaik, S.; Kishore, J.; Gunanathan, C. Cobalt-Catalyzed Acceptorless Dehydrogenation of Alcohols to Carboxylate Salts and Hydrogen. *Org. Lett.* **2020**, *22*, 1852–1857.
- (76) Dai, Z.; Luo, Q.; Jiang, H.; Luo, Q.; Li, H.; Zhang, J.; Peng, T. Ni(II)–N'NN' pincer complexes catalyzed dehydrogenation of primary alcohols to carboxylic acids and H₂ accompanied by alcohol etherification. *Catal. Sci. Technol.* **2017**, *7*, 2506–2511.
- (77) Dai, Z.; Luo, Q.; Meng, X.; Li, R.; Zhang, J.; Peng, T. Ru(II) complexes bearing 2,6-bis(benzimidazole-2-yl)pyridine ligands: A new class of catalysts for efficient dehydrogenation of primary alcohols to carboxylic acids and H₂ in the alcohol/CsOH system. *J. Organomet. Chem.* **2017**, *830*, 11–18.
- (78) Zweifel, T.; Naubron, J. V.; Grutzmacher, H. Catalyzed dehydrogenative coupling of primary alcohols with water, methanol, or amines. *Angew. Chem., Int. Ed.* **2009**, *48*, 559–563.
- (79) Paul, C.; Hanefeld, U.; Hollmann, F.; Qu, G.; Yuan, B.; Sun, Z. Enzyme engineering for biocatalysis. *Mol. Catal.* **2024**, *555*, No. 113874.
- (80) Reetz, M. Making Enzymes Suitable for Organic Chemistry by Rational Protein Design. *ChemBioChem* **2022**, *23*, No. e202200049.
- (81) Chen, K.; Arnold, F. H. Engineering new catalytic activities in enzymes. *Nat. Catal.* **2020**, *3*, 203–213.
- (82) Heath, R. S.; Birmingham, W. R.; Thompson, M. P.; Taglieber, A.; Daviet, L.; Turner, N. J. An Engineered Alcohol Oxidase for the Oxidation of Primary Alcohols. *ChemBioChem* **2019**, *20*, 276–281.
- (83) Wei, J.; Lai, M.-Y.; Li, H.-C.; Lu, X.-Y.; Xu, J.-H.; Yu, H.-L. Engineering an Unspecific Peroxygenase From *Thielavia terrestris* for Specific Terminal Oxidation of Xylene Derivatives. *ChemCatChem* **2025**, *17*, No. e202401752.
- (84) Milagre, C. D. F.; Milagre, H. M. S. Alcohol dehydrogenase-catalyzed oxidation. *Curr. Opin. Green Sustainable Chem.* **2022**, *38*, No. 100694.
- (85) Shortall, K.; Djeghader, A.; Magner, E.; Soulimane, T. Insights into Aldehyde Dehydrogenase Enzymes: A Structural Perspective. *Front. Mol. Biosci.* **2021**, *8*, No. 659550.
- (86) Contente, M. L.; Fiore, N.; Cannazza, P.; Roura Padrosa, D.; Molinari, F.; Gourlay, L.; Paradisi, F. Uncommon overoxidative catalytic activity in a new halo-tolerant alcohol dehydrogenase. *ChemCatChem* **2020**, *12*, 5679–5685.
- (87) Guengerich, F. P. Mechanisms of Cytochrome P450-Catalyzed Oxidations. *ACS Catal.* **2018**, *8*, 10964–10976.
- (88) Denisov, I. G.; Makris, T. M.; Sligar, S. G.; Schlichting, I. Structure and Chemistry of Cytochrome P450. *Chem. Rev.* **2005**, *105*, 2253–2278.
- (89) Grogan, G. Hemoprotein Catalyzed Oxygenations: P450s, UPOs, and Progress toward Scalable Reactions. *JACS Au* **2021**, *1*, 1312–1329.
- (90) Monterrey, D. T.; Menés-Rubio, A.; Keser, M.; Gonzalez-Perez, D.; Alcalde, M. Unspecific peroxygenases: The pot of gold at the end of the oxyfunctionalization rainbow? *Curr. Opin. Green Sustainable Chem.* **2023**, *41*, No. 100786.
- (91) Rotilio, L.; Swoboda, A.; Ebner, K.; Rinnofner, C.; Glieder, A.; Kroutil, W.; Mattevi, A. Structural and Biochemical Studies Enlighten the Unspecific Peroxygenase from *Hypoxylon* sp. EC38 as an Efficient Oxidative Biocatalyst. *ACS Catal.* **2021**, *11*, 11511–11525.
- (92) Chai, J.; Guo, G.; McSweeney, S. M.; Shanklin, J.; Liu, Q. Structural basis for enzymatic terminal C–H bond functionalization of alkanes. *Nat. Struct. Mol. Biol.* **2023**, *30*, 521–526.
- (93) Groves, J. T.; Feng, L.; Austin, R. N. Structure and Function of Alkane Monooxygenase (AlkB). *Acc. Chem. Res.* **2023**, *56*, 3665–3675.
- (94) Fan, G.; Gadda, G. Oxygen- and Temperature-Dependent Kinetic Isotope Effects in Choline Oxidase: Correlating Reversible Hydride Transfer with Environmentally Enhanced Tunneling. *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2005**, *127*, 17954–17961.
- (95) Pickl, M.; Fuchs, M.; Glueck, S. M.; Faber, K. The substrate tolerance of alcohol oxidases. *Appl. Microbiol. Biotechnol.* **2015**, *99*, 6617–6642.
- (96) Puetz, H.; Puchl'ová, E.; Vranková, K.; Hollmann, F. Biocatalytic Oxidation of Alcohols. *Catalysts* **2020**, *10*, No. 952.
- (97) Heath, R. S.; Turner, N. J. Recent advances in oxidase biocatalysts: Enzyme discovery, cascade reactions and scale up. *Curr. Opin. Green Sustainable Chem.* **2022**, *38*, No. 100693.
- (98) Romero, E.; Gomez Castellanos, J. R.; Gadda, G.; Fraaije, M. W.; Mattevi, A. Same Substrate, Many Reactions: Oxygen Activation in Flavoenzymes. *Chem. Rev.* **2018**, *118*, 1742–1769.
- (99) Himo, F.; Eriksson, L. A.; Maseras, F.; Siegbahn, P. E. M. Catalytic Mechanism of Galactose Oxidase: A Theoretical Study. *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2000**, *122*, 8031–8036.
- (100) Kiener, A. Enzymatic Oxidation of Methyl Groups on Aromatic Heterocycles: A Versatile Method for the Preparation of Heteroaromatic Carboxylic Acids. *Angew. Chem., Int. Ed.* **1992**, *31*, 774–775.
- (101) Deppenmeier, U.; Hoffmeister, M.; Prust, C. Biochemistry and biotechnological applications of *Gluconobacter* strains. *Appl. Microbiol. Biotechnol.* **2002**, *60*, 233–242.
- (102) Raspor, P.; Goranović, D. Biotechnological Applications of Acetic Acid Bacteria. *Crit. Rev. Biotechnol.* **2008**, *28*, 101–124.
- (103) Gandolfi, R.; Borrometi, A.; Romano, A.; Sinisterra Gago, J. V.; Molinari, F. Enantioselective oxidation of (±)-2-phenyl-1-propanol to (S)-2-phenyl-1-propionic acid with *Acetobacter aceti*: influence of medium engineering and immobilization. *Tetrahedron: Asymmetry* **2002**, *13*, 2345–2349.
- (104) Gandolfi, R.; Cavenago, K.; Gualandris, R.; Sinisterra Gago, J. V.; Molinari, F. Production of 2-phenylacetic acid and phenylacetaldehyde by oxidation of 2-phenylethanol with free immobilized cells of *Acetobacter aceti*. *Process Biochem.* **2004**, *39*, 749–753.
- (105) Brenna, E.; Cannavale, F.; Crotti, M.; De Vitis, V.; Gatti, F. G.; Migliazza, G.; Molinari, F.; Parmeggiani, F.; Romano, D.; Santangelo, S. Synthesis of Enantiomerically Enriched 2-Hydroxymethylalkanoic Acids by Oxidative Desymmetrisation of Achiral 1,3-Diols Mediated by *Acetobacter aceti*. *ChemCatChem* **2016**, *8*, 3796–3803.

- (106) Stewart, K. N.; Hicks, E. G.; Domaille, D. W. Merger of Whole Cell Biocatalysis with Organocatalysis Upgrades Alcohol Feedstocks in a Mild, Aqueous, One-Pot Process. *ACS Sustainable Chem. Eng.* **2020**, *8*, 4114–4119.
- (107) Mihal', M.; Červeňanský, I.; Markoš, J.; Rebroš, M. Bioproduction of phenylacetic acid in airlift reactor by immobilized *Gluconobacter oxydans*. *Chem. Pap.* **2017**, *71*, 103–118.
- (108) Mars, A.; Gorissen, J.; van den Beld, I.; Eggink, G. Bioconversion of limonene to increased concentrations of perillid acid by *Pseudomonas putida* GS1 in a fed-batch reactor. *Appl. Microbiol. Biotechnol.* **2001**, *56*, 101–107.
- (109) Mirata, M. A.; Heerd, D.; Schrader, J. Integrated bioprocess for the oxidation of limonene to perillid acid with *Pseudomonas putida* DSM 12264. *Process Biochem.* **2009**, *44*, 764–771.
- (110) Jia, X.; Xu, Y.; Li, Z. Regio- and Stereoselective Concurrent Oxidations with Whole Cell Biocatalyst: Simple and Green Syntheses of Enantiopure 1,2-Diols via Oxidative Kinetic Resolution. *ACS Catal.* **2011**, *1*, 591–596.
- (111) Liu, S.; Li, C.; Fang, X.; Cao, Z. Optimal pH control strategy for high-level production of long-chain α,ω -dicarboxylic acid by *Candida tropicalis*. *Enzyme Microb. Technol.* **2004**, *34*, 73–77.
- (112) Liu, Z. X.; Gao, Y. D.; Yang, L. C. Biocatalytic Hydrogen-Borrowing Cascade in Organic Synthesis. *JACS Au* **2024**, *4*, 877–892.
- (113) Grandi, E.; Feyza Ozgen, F.; Schmidt, S.; Poelarends, G. J. Enzymatic Oxy- and Amino-Functionalization in Biocatalytic Cascade Synthesis: Recent Advances and Future Perspectives. *Angew. Chem., Int. Ed.* **2023**, *62*, No. e202309012.
- (114) See, W. W. L.; Choo, J. P. S.; Jung, D.-Y.; Zhi, L. Recent developments in oxidative biocatalytic cascades. *Curr. Opin. Green Sustainable Chem.* **2022**, *38*, No. 100700.
- (115) Schrittwieser, J. H.; Velikogne, S.; Hall, M.; Kroutil, W. Artificial Biocatalytic Linear Cascades for Preparation of Organic Molecules. *Chem. Rev.* **2018**, *118*, 270–348.
- (116) Hirano, J.-i.; Miyamoto, K.; Ohta, H. The green and effective oxidation of alcohols to carboxylic acids with molecular oxygen via biocatalytic reaction. *Tetrahedron Lett.* **2008**, *49*, 1217–1219.
- (117) Wong, C. H.; Matos, J. R. Enantioselective oxidation of 1,2-diols to L- α -hydroxy acids using co-immobilized alcohol and aldehyde dehydrogenases as catalysts. *J. Org. Chem.* **1985**, *50*, 1992–1994.
- (118) Liu, K.; Jiang, L.; Wang, L.; Zhang, Q.; Yang, L.; Wu, J.; Yu, H. Sequential single-enzyme oxidation of 5-hydroxymethylfurfural to 2,5-furandicarboxylic acid by an engineered lanthanide-dependent alcohol dehydrogenase. *Green Chem.* **2025**, *27*, 5073–5090.
- (119) Velasco-Lozano, S.; Santiago-Arcos, J.; Grazia Rubanu, M.; Lopez-Gallego, F. Cell-Free Biosynthesis of ω -Hydroxy Acids Boosted by a Synergistic Combination of Alcohol Dehydrogenases. *ChemSusChem* **2022**, *15*, No. e202200397.
- (120) Jia, H. Y.; Zong, M. H.; Zheng, G. W.; Li, N. One-Pot Enzyme Cascade for Controlled Synthesis of Furancarboxylic Acids from 5-Hydroxymethylfurfural by H₂O₂ Internal Recycling. *ChemSusChem* **2019**, *12*, 4764–4768.
- (121) Nigl, A.; Delsoglio, V.; Sovic, L.; Grgić, M.; Malihan-Yap, L.; Myrtollari, K.; Spasic, J.; Winkler, M.; Oberdorfer, G.; Taden, A.; et al. Engineering of Transmembrane Alkane Monooxygenases to Improve a Key Reaction Step in the Synthesis of Polymer Precursor Tulipalin A. *Angew. Chem., Int. Ed.* **2025**, *64*, No. e202503464.
- (122) Lim, S.; Yoo, H.-w.; Sarak, S.; Kim, B.-g.; Yun, H. A multi-enzyme cascade reaction for the production of α,ω -dicarboxylic acids from free fatty acids. *J. Ind. Eng. Chem.* **2021**, *98*, 358–365.
- (123) Jang, J.-H.; Choi, K.-Y. Whole Cell Biotransformation of 1-dodecanol by *Escherichia coli* by Soluble Expression of ADH Enzyme from *Yarrowia lipolytica*. *Biotechnol. Bioprocess Eng.* **2021**, *26*, 247–255.
- (124) Sripattanakul, S.; Chueakwon, P.; Trinh, L. T. T.; Lai, R.-Y. Nicotinic acid production from 3-methylpyridine by *E. coli* whole-cell biocatalyst. *Enzyme Microb. Technol.* **2025**, *190*, No. 110682.
- (125) Han, Y.; Geng, N.; Sha, J.; Li, H.; You, C.; Liu, W.; Zhang, J.; Shi, J.; Wu, X.; Zhang, W. Aldehyde Dehydrogenase from *Klebsiella pneumoniae*: A Robust Biocatalyst for Preparing Heteroatom-Containing Carboxylic Acids. *Adv. Synth. Catal.* **2025**, *367*, No. e202500027.
- (126) Urlacher, V. B.; Girhard, M. Cytochrome P450 Monooxygenases in Biotechnology and Synthetic Biology. *Trends Biotechnol.* **2019**, *37*, 882–897.
- (127) Hannemann, F.; Bichet, A.; Ewen, K. M.; Bernhardt, R. Cytochrome P450 systems—biological variations of electron transport chains. *Biochim. Biophys. Acta, Gen. Subj.* **2007**, *1770*, 330–344.
- (128) Schewe, H.; Kaup, B.-A.; Schrader, J. Improvement of P450BM-3 whole-cell biocatalysis by integrating heterologous cofactor regeneration combining glucose facilitator and dehydrogenase in *E. coli*. *Appl. Microbiol. Biotechnol.* **2008**, *78*, 55–65.
- (129) Mouri, T.; Michizoe, J.; Ichinose, H.; Kamiya, N.; Goto, M. A recombinant *Escherichia coli* whole cell biocatalyst harboring a cytochrome P450cam monooxygenase system coupled with enzymatic cofactor regeneration. *Appl. Microbiol. Biotechnol.* **2006**, *72*, 514–520.
- (130) Bell-Parikh, L. C.; Guengerich, F. P. Kinetics of cytochrome P450 2E1-catalyzed oxidation of ethanol to acetic acid via acetaldehyde. *J. Biol. Chem.* **1999**, *274*, 23833–23840.
- (131) Funhoff, E.; Bauer, G.; García-Rubio, U.; Witholt, I.; van Beilen, B. Jan, B. CYP153A6, a Soluble P450 Oxygenase Catalyzing Terminal-Alkane Hydroxylation. *J. Bacteriol.* **2006**, *188*, 5220–5227.
- (132) Hausjell, J.; Halbwrith, H.; Spadiut, O. Recombinant production of eukaryotic cytochrome P450s in microbial cell factories. *Biosci. Rep.* **2018**, *38*, No. BSR20171290.
- (133) Cali, J. J.; Russell, D. W. Characterization of human sterol 27-hydroxylase. A mitochondrial cytochrome P-450 that catalyzes multiple oxidation reaction in bile acid biosynthesis. *J. Biol. Chem.* **1991**, *266*, 7774–7778.
- (134) Le Bouquin, R.; Skrabs, M.; Kahn, R.; Benveniste, I.; Salaün, J.-P.; Schreiber, L.; Durst, F.; Pinot, F. CYP94A5, a new cytochrome P450 from *Nicotiana tabacum* is able to catalyze the oxidation of fatty acids to the ω -alcohol and to the corresponding diacid. *Eur. J. Biochem.* **2001**, *268*, 3083–3090.
- (135) Ro, D. K.; Paradise, E. M.; Ouellet, M.; Fisher, K. J.; Newman, K. L.; Ndungu, J. M.; Ho, K. A.; Eachus, R. A.; Ham, T. S.; Kirby, J.; et al. Production of the antimalarial drug precursor artemisinic acid in engineered yeast. *Nature* **2006**, *440*, 940–943.
- (136) Iizaka, Y.; Sherman, D. H.; Anzai, Y. An overview of the cytochrome P450 enzymes that catalyze the same-site multistep oxidation reactions in biotechnologically relevant selected actinomycete strains. *Appl. Microbiol. Biotechnol.* **2021**, *105*, 2647–2661.
- (137) Iizaka, Y.; Kanai, H.; Suzuki, T.; Maruyama, Y.; Kurita, M.; Sano, M.; Watanabe, A.; Fukumoto, A.; Saito, R.; Anzai, Y. Artificial control of the multistep oxidation reactions catalyzed by the cytochrome P450 enzyme RosC. *Appl. Microbiol. Biotechnol.* **2020**, *104*, 3403–3415.
- (138) Bühler, B.; Witholt, B.; Hauer, B.; Schmid, A. Characterization and application of xylene monooxygenase for multistep biocatalysis. *Appl. Environ. Microbiol.* **2002**, *68*, 560–568.
- (139) Grant, C.; Deszcz, D.; Wei, Y.-C.; Martínez-Torres, R. J.; Morris, P.; Folliard, T.; Sreenivasan, R.; Ward, J.; Dalby, P.; Woodley, J. M.; et al. Identification and use of an alkane transporter plug-in for applications in biocatalysis and whole-cell biosensing of alkanes. *Sci. Rep.* **2014**, *4*, No. 5844.
- (140) van Nuland, Y. M.; de Vogel, F. A.; Scott, E. L.; Eggink, G.; Weusthuis, R. A. Biocatalytic, one-pot diterminal oxidation and esterification of *n*-alkanes for production of α,ω -diol and α,ω -dicarboxylic acid esters. *Metab. Eng.* **2017**, *44*, 134–142.
- (141) Puetz, H.; Puchl'ová, E.; Vranková, K.; Hollmann, F. Biocatalytic Oxidation of Alcohols. *Catalysts* **2020**, *10*, No. 952.
- (142) Wahart, A. J. C.; Staniland, J.; Miller, G. J.; Cosgrove, S. C. Oxidase enzymes as sustainable oxidation catalysts. *R. Soc. Open Sci.* **2022**, *9*, No. 211572.
- (143) Al-Shameri, A.; Schmermund, L.; Sieber, V. Current Advances in the Enzyme Engineering of O₂-Dependent Enzymes – Boosting the Versatility and Applicability of Oxygenases and Oxidases. *ChemCatChem* **2024**, *16*, No. e202301109.

- (144) Toftgaard Pedersen, A.; Birmingham, W. R.; Rehn, G.; Charnock, S. J.; Turner, N. J.; Woodley, J. M. Process Requirements of Galactose Oxidase Catalyzed Oxidation of Alcohols. *Org. Process Res. Dev.* **2015**, *19*, 1580–1589.
- (145) Dijkman, W. P.; Groothuis, D. E.; Fraaije, M. W. Enzyme-catalyzed oxidation of 5-hydroxymethylfurfural to furan-2,5-dicarboxylic acid. *Angew. Chem., Int. Ed.* **2014**, *53*, 6515–6518.
- (146) Pickl, M.; Winkler, C. K.; Glueck, S. M.; Fraaije, M. W.; Faber, K. Rational Engineering of a Flavoprotein Oxidase for Improved Direct Oxidation of Alcohols to Carboxylic Acids. *Molecules* **2017**, *22*, No. 2205.
- (147) Martin, C.; Trajkovic, M.; Fraaije, M. W. Production of Hydroxy Acids: Selective Double Oxidation of Diols by Flavoprotein Alcohol Oxidase. *Angew. Chem., Int. Ed.* **2020**, *59*, 4869–4872.
- (148) Birmingham, W. R.; Turner, N. J. A Single Enzyme Oxidative “Cascade” via a Dual-Functional Galactose Oxidase. *ACS Catal.* **2018**, *8*, 4025–4032.
- (149) Bechi, B.; Herter, S.; McKenna, S.; Riley, C.; Leimkühler, S.; Turner, N. J.; Carnell, A. J. Catalytic bio–chemo and bio–bio tandem oxidation reactions for amide and carboxylic acid synthesis. *Green Chem.* **2014**, *16*, 4524–4529.
- (150) McKenna, S. M.; Leimkühler, S.; Herter, S.; Turner, N. J.; Carnell, A. J. Enzyme cascade reactions: synthesis of furandicarboxylic acid (FDCA) and carboxylic acids using oxidases in tandem. *Green Chem.* **2015**, *17*, 3271–3275.
- (151) Ullrich, R.; Nuske, J.; Scheibner, K.; Spantzel, J.; Hofrichter, M. Novel haloperoxidase from the agaric basidiomycete *Agrocybe aegerita* oxidizes aryl alcohols and aldehydes. *Appl. Environ. Microbiol.* **2004**, *70*, 4575–4581.
- (152) Hofrichter, M.; Ullrich, R. Oxidations catalyzed by fungal peroxygenases. *Curr. Opin. Chem. Biol.* **2014**, *19*, 116–125.
- (153) Swoboda, A.; Zwölfer, S.; Duhović, Z.; Bürgler, M.; Ebner, K.; Glieder, A.; Kroutil, W. Multistep Biooxidation of 5-(Hydroxymethyl)furfural to 2,5-Furandicarboxylic Acid with H₂O₂ by Unspecific Peroxygenases. *ChemSusChem* **2024**, *17*, No. e202400156.
- (154) Pogrányi, B.; Mielke, T.; Cartwright, J.; Unsworth, W. P.; Grogan, G. Selective Oxidations of Toluenes and Benzyl Alcohols by an Unspecific Peroxygenase (UPO). *ChemCatChem* **2024**, *16*, No. e202400702.
- (155) Podgorski, M. N.; Bell, S. G. Comparing and Combining Alternative Strategies for Enhancing Cytochrome P450 Peroxygenase Activity. *ACS Catal.* **2025**, *15*, 5191–5210.
- (156) Melling, B.; Mielke, T.; Whitwood, A. C.; O’Riordan, T. J. C.; Mulholland, N.; Cartwright, J.; Unsworth, W. P.; Grogan, G. Complementary specificity of unspecific peroxygenases enables access to diverse products from terpene oxygenation. *Chem. Catal.* **2024**, *4*, No. 100889.
- (157) Li, J.; Duran, C.; Pogranyi, B.; Cornish, K. A. S.; Cartwright, J.; Osuna, S.; Unsworth, W. P.; Grogan, G. Divergent Oxidation Reactions of *E*- and *Z*-Allylic Primary Alcohols by an Unspecific Peroxygenase. *Angew. Chem., Int. Ed.* **2025**, *64*, No. e202422241.
- (158) Munro, A. W.; McLean, K. J.; Grant, J. L.; Makris, T. M. Structure and function of the cytochrome P450 peroxygenase enzymes. *Biochem. Soc. Trans.* **2018**, *46*, 183–196.
- (159) Bangert, K.; Swoboda, A.; Vrabl, S.; Rudalija, H.; Lazzarotto, M.; Payer, S.; Glieder, A.; van Slagmaat, C. A. M. R.; De Wildeman, S. M. A.; Kroutil, W. Preparative regio- and stereoselective α -hydroxylation of medium chain mono- and dicarboxylic fatty acids. *Green Chem.* **2024**, *26*, 3183–3189.
- (160) Zhao, P.; Kong, F.; Jiang, Y.; Qin, X.; Tian, X.; Cong, Z. Enabling Peroxygenase Activity in Cytochrome P450 Monooxygenases by Engineering Hydrogen Peroxide Tunnels. *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2023**, *145*, 5506–5511.
- (161) Kinner, A.; Rosenthal, K.; Lütz, S. Identification and Expression of New Unspecific Peroxygenases – Recent Advances, Challenges and Opportunities. *Front. Bioeng. Biotechnol.* **2021**, *9*, No. 705630.
- (162) Last, S.; Heinks, T.; Dietz, N.; Koopmeiners, S.; Fischer von Mollard, G.; Weissenborn, M. J.; von Langermann, J. Constant Enzymatic in situ Production of H₂O₂ for an Unspecific Peroxygenase by an L-Amino Acid Oxidase. *Adv. Synth. Catal.* **2025**, *367*, No. e202500105.
- (163) Freakley, S. J.; Kochius, S.; van Marwijk, J.; Fenner, C.; Lewis, R. J.; Baldenius, K.; Marais, S. S.; Opperman, D. J.; Harrison, S. T. L.; Alcalde, M.; et al. A chemo-enzymatic oxidation cascade to activate C–H bonds with in situ generated H₂O₂. *Nat. Commun.* **2019**, *10*, No. 4178.
- (164) Swoboda, A.; Pfeifenberger, L. J.; Duhovic, Z.; Burgler, M.; Oroz-Guinea, I.; Bangert, K.; Weissensteiner, F.; Parigger, L.; Ebner, K.; Glieder, A.; et al. Enantioselective High-Throughput Assay Showcased for the Identification of (*R*)- as well as (*S*)-Selective Unspecific Peroxygenases for C-H Oxidation. *Angew. Chem., Int. Ed.* **2023**, *62*, No. e202312721.
- (165) Al-Shameri, A.; Siebert, D. L.; Sutiono, S.; Lauterbach, L.; Sieber, V. Hydrogenase-based oxidative biocatalysis without oxygen. *Nat. Commun.* **2023**, *14*, No. 2693.
- (166) Ruff, A.; Conzuelo, F.; Schuhmann, W. Bioelectrocatalysis as the basis for the design of enzyme-based biofuel cells and semi-artificial biophotocatalysts. *Nat. Catal.* **2020**, *3*, 214–224.
- (167) Chen, H.; Dong, F.; Minteer, S. D. The progress and outlook of bioelectrocatalysis for the production of chemicals, fuels and materials. *Nat. Catal.* **2020**, *3*, 225–244.
- (168) Ma, C.; Wang, Y.; Guo, K.; Wu, R.; Zhu, Z. Enzymatic electrosynthesis system based on multi-enzyme catalysis or coupled with microbial transformation. *Catal. Sci. Technol.* **2025**, *15*, 1390–1405.
- (169) Tufvesson, P.; Lima-Ramos, J.; Nordblad, M.; Woodley, J. M. Guidelines and Cost Analysis for Catalyst Production in Biocatalytic Processes. *Org. Process Res. Dev.* **2011**, *15*, 266–274.